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THE SIGNIFICANCE OF IDENTITY FOR CONFLICT RESOLUTION

**EMPIRICAL EVIDENCE
FROM
A COMPUTER SIMULATION
MODELING THE
ISRAELI-PALESTINIAN CONFLICT**

*Faculty of Behavioral and Cultural Studies
at the University of Heidelberg*

Diploma thesis by
Alena Hannah Mehlau

Advisor: Prof. Dr. Joachim Funke
Second Advisor: Prof. Dr. Klaus Fiedler

Heidelberg, February 2011

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I hereby agree that after the completion of my diploma degree my thesis

**«THE SIGNIFICANCE OF IDENTITY FOR CONFLICT RESOLUTION:
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MODELING THE ISRAELI-PALESTINIAN CONFLICT»**

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ABSTRACT

A flexible, open thinking-style is known to facilitate conflict resolution progress. However, actors often think in a *closed-minded* way, thereby impeding it. This study aimed to examine the extent to which a strong association of persons' personal and social identity with the conflict explains closed-mindedness. Identity, defined here over religion, geo-cultural origin, values and social affiliation, plays an important role in today's political conflict landscape. 124 participants attempted to solve the Israeli-Palestinian conflict in the commercial computer game *PeaceMaker*. In doing so, high identity-associated participants showed a closed processing mode. They relied more on general conflict schemata, accessed less information sources and showed worse performance in a delayed recall test about features of the game than low identity associated participants. They also experienced a stronger emotional reaction to the conflict situation in terms of higher levels of affective arousal and stronger decreases in pleasantness ratings as compared to the lowly associated group. A Latent Growth Curve Modeling approach combined with hierarchical multiple regressions revealed that affect was playing a mediating role in the relationship between identity association on the one hand and information search and recall on the other. I discuss these findings against the backdrop of theories on the relation between affect and problem solving and derive suggestions for the conflict resolution and mediation practice.

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«FOR TOO LONG, THE PALESTINIAN PEOPLE HAVE GONE UNHEEDED, SILENCED AND DENIED, OUR IDENTITY NEGATED BY POLITICAL EXPEDIENCE, OUR RIGHT FOR STRUGGLE AGAINST INJUSTICE MALIGNED, AND OUR PRESENT EXISTENCE SUBSUMED BY THE PAST TRAGEDY OF ANOTHER PEOPLE» Haidar Abd El-Shafi, head of the Palestinian Delegation to the Madrid Peace Conference, Opening Remarks; Madrid, 30 October, 1991 (The Madrid Peace Conference, 1992).

«OUR RIGHT TO BUILD OUR SOVEREIGN STATE HERE, IN THE LAND OF ISRAEL, ARISES FROM ONE SIMPLE FACT: THIS IS THE HOMELAND OF THE JEWISH PEOPLE, THIS IS WHERE OUR IDENTITY WAS FORGED» Benjamin Netanyahu, Israeli Prime Minister, seminal address at Bar-Ilan University, 14 June, 2009 (AIPAC, 2009).

1 INTRODUCTION

In 2010, the Heidelberg Institute for International Conflict Research classified 269 out of 363 conflicts as intra-state conflicts (Heidelberg Institute for International Conflict Research, 2010). In intra-state conflicts, political leaders use identity variables like religion, ethnicity or values to mobilize their followers and to legitimize their claim for conflict items (Schrader, 2008). Identity has become a central component of political conflicts and it has become clear that in order to achieve reconciliation, the conflict parties' identities need to change (Kelman, 2006). Therefore, conflict research urges practitioners to consider not only factual interests but also identities in conflict resolution (e.g., Galtung, 1998; Kim, Kollontai, & Hoyland, 2008). Given the importance of identity in today's conflict landscape, it is crucial to know how the involvement of identity influences the way someone approaches a conflict. And yet there is a lack of empirical research addressing this issue. In order to fill this gap, the current paper aimed to provide some preliminary insights into the relationship between identity and conflict, based on the data collected in a controlled laboratory study. PeaceMaker, a computer simulation of the Israeli-Palestinian case, was used to assess conflict resolution behavior. In the Israeli-Palestinian confrontation, many scholars see an example in which the role of identity is particularly salient (e.g. Gabay, 2006; Hofman & Rouhana, 1976; Rouhana, 1999).

«EACH GROUP'S IDENTITY [IS] HOSTAGE TO THE IDENTITY OF THE OTHER: SINCE ITS

OWN IDENTITY THRIVES TO THE EXTENT THAT THE OTHER'S IDENTITY LANGUISHES, IT MUST INVEST GREAT ENERGY IN DISCREDITING THE OTHER» summarized Kelman the significance of identity for the Israeli-Palestinian conflict (1999, p. 589).

The PeaceMaker computer scenario of Israel-Palestine was thus highly appropriate for the research topic in question: the significance of identity for conflict resolution. By being associated to someone's identity, a conflict becomes highly relevant to the self. This, I supposed, must lead to a conflict resolution style different from conflict resolution without identity association. Conflict resolution is facilitated when the actors involved open up to new perspectives and evidence. Closed-minded adherence to pre-existing beliefs and stereotypes in contrast heavily obstructs conflict resolution progress (Carnevale & Probst, 1998). I aimed to show that, unfortunately, identity association with a conflict makes such a closed thinking style very likely, even if the commitment to advance the conflict resolution prevails. The closed-mindedness should be at least in part explainable by affective mechanisms as "behavior indicating involvement of the self in psychological processing is typically emotional" (Sherif, Kelly, Rodgers, Sarup, & Tittler, 1973, p. 312). Lefford noted in 1946:

«THE DISASTROUS EFFECTS OF EMOTIONAL THINKING CAN BE FOUND EVERYWHERE (...) THE PROBLEM IS ESPECIALLY ACUTE TODAY, IN A WAR-TORN WORLD, WHERE ONLY ACTION BASED ON OBJECTIVITY OF ANALYSIS AND RATIONALITY OF THOUGHT CAN LEAD TO A SUCCESSFUL SOLUTION OF THE SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC PROBLEMS (...)» (p. 127).

Conflicts involving wars and violence continue to be widespread, but since the pioneer works by Robert Zajonc (1980) and Gordon Bower (1981), the image of emotions has changed. Today, there is considerable agreement that affective states can be advantageous for some problem solving tasks (e.g., Isen, 2001; Schwarz & Bless, 1991) and sometimes facilitate normatively correct decisions (Bechara, Damasio, Tranel, & Damasio, 1997). On the other side, also the disadvantageous influence of affect was corroborated by further evidence (e.g., Derakshan & Eysenck, 2010). The impact of affect clearly depends on the specific characteristics of the affective experience (e.g., its source). I expected affect resulting from identity association to be detrimental to problem solving advancement by contributing to a closed-minded processing mode.

As laboratory research on conflict resolution behavior is wearing children's shoes, I understood this study as an exploratory endeavor. The goal was to examine the explanatory value of affect and to gain some tentative insight into which aspects of identity and conflict resolution behavior would be promising for further research. Most crucially perhaps, this study aimed to demonstrate that controlled laboratory research with a proper theoretical base can yield findings highly relevant for real-world conflicts.

2 THEORETICAL RATIONALE

I will explain why identity association is assumed to be linked to closed-mindedness and why affect is a likely mediator of this relationship. Figure 1 depicts the relations between the variables. Before deriving my hypotheses (2.5), the variables are conceptually introduced. Each is defined more precisely by two sub-features: Social and personal identities are constitutive for a more general identity concept (2.1); conflict resolution is understood on the one hand as a subjective experience and as a complex problem solving on the other (2.2); affect is defined by the dimensions of valence and arousal (2.4). Furthermore, this section presents the conflict simulation used (2.3).

Figure 1. Theoretical rationale of this thesis.

2.1 SOCIAL AND PERSONAL IDENTITY

In the statements cited at the beginning of this paper, Netanyahu and El-Shafi expressed identification with their nation. Belonging to a nation constitutes a part of a person's *social identity*. According to the social identity theory (Turner, 1982; Tajfel & Turner, 1986) and the self-categorization theory (Turner, 1985; Turner, Hogg, Oakes, Reicher, & Wetherell, 1987), the self is to a big extent determined by social identifications

in the form of group memberships and inter-group relations (Turner, 1975).¹ Social categories like religion, ethnicity, geo-cultural origin or gender are used by individuals to define themselves (Hogg, 2006). In the case of the Israeli-Palestinian conflict, a variety of research has shown the importance of social identity variables for beliefs about the peace process (e.g., Hermann & Yuchtman-Yaar, 2002; Mollov & Lavie, 2001). Also, in case of other political conflicts, social identity has proven its high explanatory value (e.g., Cairns, 1982, for Northern Ireland). I assumed that religion, geo-cultural origin and - most straightforwardly - self-reported affiliation with a conflict party would be the social identifications most relevant for conflict resolution in the Israeli-Palestinian case.

However, a person's identity also includes characteristics that are not immediately determined by social identifications, referred to as *personal identity*. According to John C. Turner, social identities and personal identities together constitute the self-concept. His idea of personal identity as "specific attributes of the individual such as feelings of competence, bodily attributes, ways of relating to others, psychological characteristics, intellectual concerns (...)" (Turner, 1982, p. 18), is too broad to be clearly distinct from social identities. Hitlin (2003) offered a more precise conceptualization. He defined personal identity with a person's value-structure. The importance of values for the self-concept has been emphasized by various researchers. For instance, Ralph Turner noted: "The self-conception starts with values and aspirations, and continues to be represented in value and aspiration terms" (1968, p. 97). Values can be understood as beliefs "about how [people] ought or ought not to behave, or about some end-state of existence worth or not worth attaining" (Rokeach, 1968, p. 124). They are said to be the standards guiding the development of the self and thus an important factor for the creation of a sense of self-identity (Ibid).

A principal feature of values is that they transcend specific situations (Schwartz, 1994) and thereby create a "unified, trans-situational personal identity" (Hitlin, 2003, p. 122). It is the personal identity which conveys feelings of individual continuity, autonomy

¹ Apart from social identity theory, identity theory (Burke & Reitzes, 1981) is also useful to capture social aspects of the self. However, a comprehensive discussion of the variations in the identity concept is beyond the scope of this paper.

and uniqueness. By contrast, an individual's different social identities form a dialectic relationship with social situations; their salience varies from setting to setting, and sometimes even changes within one social situation.² The continuity lacking in social identity theory is the core element of a value-based personal identity concept. Obviously, personal identity and social identity are not independent from each other. Deaux, in an attempt to integrate social and personal identity theories, saw personal identities reflected in someone's particular ways of expressing group membership (Reid & Deaux, 1996). Values are enacted in interpersonal interactions and "to a large extent derived, learned and internalized by society" (Rokeach, 1979, p. 6).

For a holistic assessment of the identity construct, this study is concerned with values as well as social identifications. Following Johnson and Eagly, I will refer to a relationship between values and conflict as *value-based involvement*, "the psychological state that is created by the activation of attitudes that are linked to important values" (1989, p. 290).³ Values, affiliation felt with a group, religion and geo-cultural origin all cover a distinct nuance of a possible association between the self and a political conflict, but are obviously interrelated. Religion is linked to origin, and both are crucial for the developments of affiliations and values. However, their inter-dependencies are not deterministic; e.g., variance in affiliation and values is attributable to a multitude of sources. Including these different aspects of identity does not create redundancies but does justice to the complexity of the identity construct.

Identity influences to which extent and in which way an issue is related to the self. In the Israeli-Palestinian case, a special self-conflict association is given for those with roots in the Middle East, for Muslims and Jews, for those who feel a general affiliation with the Palestinian or Israeli side, and for persons whose value system is related to the

² This is exactly why Abrams criticized: "Social identity theory and self-categorization theory have both neglected the question of how people retain psychological continuity when making transitions from behaving as a member of group X to behaving as a member of group Y, or indeed how and whether groups X and Y are psychologically integrated as components of the self" (1996, p. 144).

³ Categorizations of different types of involvement (e.g., Boninger, Krosnick & Berent, 1995; Johnson & Eagly, 1989) follow William James' tripartite theory (1890). They distinguish outcome-relevant involvement (material aspects of the self), impression-relevant involvement (social aspects of the self) and value-relevant involvement (spiritual aspects of the self).

conflict. The identity association should impact participants' perception of the conflict and their attempts to solve it.

2.2 CONFLICT RESOLUTION

I define conflict resolution following Deutsch (2001) as including all activities - constructive or destructive - that aim at terminating or mitigating a conflict situation.⁴ Conflict and conflict resolution are subjective experiences (2.2.1) and represent a highly complex problem for the conflict resolver (2.2.2).

2.2.1 *Subjective experience*

Identity association, I suppose, influences conflict resolution behavior by having an effect upon how intense the conflict is perceived, i.e. upon how incompatible the parties' goals appear to the persons involved. When goals are perceived as strongly incompatible, an interactional dynamic arises that revolves "around the perception of threat and an affective reaction to the perceived threat" (Hammer, 2001, p. 60). There is considerable agreement in the field about perception, affect, and a dynamic antagonistic relationship being fundamental components of conflict. Sandole (1993), for instance, captured conflict as "a dynamic phenomenon (...), a situation in which at least two actors, or their representatives, try to pursue their *perceptions* of mutually incompatible goals by undermining, directly or indirectly, the goal-seeking capability of one another" (Sandole, 1993, p. 3). Nearly a classic in literature, Fink conceptualized conflict as "any social situation or process in which two or more social entities are linked by at least one form of *antagonistic psychological relation* or at least one form of antagonistic interaction" (1968, p. 456). The affective component of conflict represents a main focus in the recent literature on conflict and negotiation (Bilsky, Müller, Voss, & von Groote, 2005; Hipel, Obeidi, & Kilgour, 2005; Lindner, 2006). To recap, (1) individual perceptions determine

⁴ Influential authors like Kelman (2006), Rouhana (1999) or Bar-Tal (2000) are committed to an understanding of conflict resolution as being distinct from other processes like conflict settlement and reconciliation. I agree, however, such detailed differentiation would go beyond the scope of this paper.

whether a conflict is given and (2) depending on the cognitive appraisal (e.g., a threat appraisal) an affective reaction ensues. In section 2.5, I will make some suggestions about how identity association impacts appraisals and affect.

2.2.2 *Complex Problem*

A conflict is (1) highly *complex* and (2) developing *dynamically*. The conflict solver needs (3) to consider a multitude of mutually independent aspects (*connectivity of variables*) and can (4) never fully comprehend all the influences inherent in the situation (*intransparency*). Moreover, she (5) has to balance multiple goals and conflicting interests (*polytely*). The **Complex Problem Solving (CPS)** pioneer Dörner (1986) defined these features as constitutive for complex problems (cf. Funke, 1991, 2001; Quesada, Kintsch, & Gomez, 2005). Conflicts being understood as complex problems, acts of conflict resolution are Complex Problem Solving behavior. CPS behavior occurs “to overcome barriers between a given state and a desired goal state by means of behavioral and/or cognitive, multistep activities”⁵ (Frensch & Funke, 1995, p. 18; for a conflict resolution as problem solving perspective see Long & Brecke, 2003). Also, real-world decision makers need to overcome various obstacles on their way to goal achievement in a multistep decision sequence (Walcott, 1980). Not coincidentally, classical problem solving models (Figure 2) parallel conceptualizations of conflict resolution (Figure 3). Against the backdrop of these parallels, theories and findings of CPS can be validly applied to conflict resolution research. Of special relevance for this study, CPS research has been addressing the influence of affect (Otto & Lantermann, 2004; Spring, Wagener, & Funke, 2005) and inter-individual difference variables (cf. Schoppek & Putz-Osterloh, 2003) on higher level cognition. For illustration, take a comparative look at the following models of Complex Problem Solving and conflict resolution:

⁵ The authors assume further: “The given state, goal state, and barriers between given state and goal state are complex, change dynamically during problem solving, and are intransparent. The exact properties of the given state, goal state, and barriers are unknown to the solver at the outset. CPS implies the efficient interaction between a solver and the situational requirements of the task, and involves a solver’s cognitive, emotional, personal, and social abilities” (Frensch & Funke, 1995, p. 18).

Figure 2. Phases of action regulation in problem solving. Based on Dörner & Wearing, 1995.

Figure 3. The conflict resolution model by Levi & Benjamin, 1977.

Note. Both models postulate that after defining the problem or conflict, information is collected in order to develop possible solutions and to decide which alternative to choose. Levi and Benjamin (1977) assume reciprocal processes for conflict resolution like Dörner and Wearing (1995) do for CPS: New information acquired can make it necessary to redefine the situation and to change the ways of decision making.

CPS research has been using computer-simulated scenarios of real-world problems, called “microworlds”, for nearly 30 years (e.g., Berry & Broadbent, 1984; Dörner, 1981, 1989; Funke, 1988; Güss, Tuason, & Gerhard, 2010; Putz-Osterloh & Lemme, 1987). Also, in the field of international relations and conflict resolution, computer simulations are popular. Examples date back to the 1950s (e.g., Goldhamer & Speier, 1959; Guetzkow, 1959; Guetzkow & Jensen, 1966; Starkey & Blake, 2001). However, in contrast to CPS, the scenarios used here were oversimplifying the reality, the vast majority of them being rooted in game theory and applying “prisoners’ dilemma”

modifications (e.g., Deutsch, Epstein, Canavan, & Grumpert, 1967; Fang, Hipel, & Kilgour, 1993; Kuperman, 2010; Pilisuk, 1984; Rousseau, 1999; Steeb & Johnston, 1981). The prisoners' dilemma type of simulation is too simple to be generalizable for conflicts in reality. External validity suffered. Moreover, most computer-based studies on conflict resolution did not take psychological theorizing into account or - due to a background in traditional cognitive psychology - neglected the important affective component of conflict (e.g., Mintz, 1997; Stein & Welch, 1997).

The present laboratory study explicitly addresses cognitive as well as affective processes and explains conflict resolution behavior in a theory-guided manner. Owing to the controlled setting in the laboratory that restricts the influence of confounding variables, the internal validity is high. External validity is also given since today's information technology allows for the creation of elaborated conflict simulations like PeaceMaker. In these simulations, complex realities are not oversimplified (on the advantages of microworlds see Brehmer, 1992; Brehmer & Dörner, 1993). Thanks to the high degree of realism of these semantically rich scenarios, psychological variables such as affect can be studied in laboratory settings very well.

2.3 THE PEACEMAKER GAME

So far, I have shown that a conflict is a complex problem, which is perceived differently by persons. In this section, the conflict simulation is introduced. Different conflict resolution strategies can be identified within Peacemaker. These are defined in section 2.3.2.

2.3.1 *Scenario characteristics*

The Complex Problem Solving scenario PeaceMaker is a strategy video game developed at Carnegie Mellon University, Pittsburgh, USA, under the lead of the former graduate students Eric Brown and Israeli-born Asi Burak. In the development process, the team incorporated advice of reviewers with Israeli as well as Palestinian background. The award-winning game (Games for Change Annual Contest, 2007, USC's public diplomacy

games contest, 2006) was launched in 2007 under the label ImpactGames (ImpactGames, 2008). It has received considerable acclaim in the media (Al-Jazeera, 2007; Fox News, 2008; Israeli Channel 2, 2007; Thompson, 2006; Time Magazine, 2006). In order to capitalize on its educational value, the game has been included in the curriculum at Carnegie Mellon University and the Peres Center for Peace distributed more than 80.000 copies in the Middle East (Peres Center for Peace, 2007).

PeaceMaker is available in English, Hebrew and Arabic. Hence, sufficient English knowledge was set as a condition for participation in this study and English proficiency was controlled in the statistical analysis. Besides, participants were equipped with a sheet of translated core terms. In the game, the player can adopt the position of the Israeli Prime Minister (PM) or Palestinian Authority President. As given in reality, the roles are completely different and not comparable. Because of the constraints with regard to the total duration of the study, time was not sufficient to let participants explore both roles in depth. All participants assumed the role of the Israeli PM.

A successful Prime Minister considers the interests of the Israeli as well as Palestinian side simultaneously. The approval of these two reference groups is expressed in two scores. When both the Israeli and the Palestinian score approach 100 points, a two-state solution is achieved and the player wins the game. If Palestinian or Israeli score drops below -50 a third Intifada erupts or the PM is removed from the office – the game is lost. In order to gain the different groups' approval, the right actions need to be taken (see Figure 4). The gamer chooses between security, political and construction actions, with different options in each action category (e.g. security option: send police units, political: speak to the Israeli people, construction: give education aid). Some of these actions create a win-win situation, others a win-lose situation.

Figure 4. The PeaceMaker interface.

Following on an action, with a simulated gap of one week's time, feedback on the action's aftermath is given. Information sources help to choose an appropriate action (see Figure 5). Subsumed under the category *polls*, one learns for instance how much sympathy the Israeli public feels for the Palestinians or how safe the Israelis feel in their country. Even more useful is the *groups* category that provides information about how far internal and external actors approve of the player's course of action (actors are the Israeli and Palestinian public, the Palestinian president, militant groups, the Yesha settlers' council, the US, the UN and the Arab World). The PeaceMaker interface, where actions, groups and polls are embedded, is a map of Israel's central area, the Gaza Strip and the West Bank.

Beyond the player's control there are positive, negative and neutral events taking place during the game, such as militant attacks, protests, initiatives by certain actors and so forth. These incidents are visualized via pictures and videos from real news reports. The high realism of the events' presentation contributes to the emotional loading of the PeaceMaker game. Moreover, the game features a soundtrack creating a tense, menacing atmosphere. The participants listened to the music via headphones. Gaming activity was

followed with log files. They registered changes in the approval scores, all actions taken and all groups and polls viewed.

Figure 5. The window of a groups information source: Approval of the United Nations.

2.3.2 Conflict resolution strategies

Since gaming time in this study was at the maximum 35 minutes, participants spent most of the time in the second problem solving stage of “information collection and hypothesis formation” (Dörner & Wearing, 1995; see Figure 2). This exploratory stadium is of fundamental importance in Complex Problem Solving and real-world conflict resolution. Information should be acquired about possible causalities and the internal structure of the (conflict) scenario and hypotheses on how to solve the problem should be built. However, participants may also prefer not to do so, eschewing from this capacity-demanding, information-based strategy⁶. Most dual-process models (see Chaiken & Trope, 1999, for a collection) assume that decisions are made based on more or less capacity-demanding cognitive processes.⁷ The less effortful strategy is described

⁶ Strategies are recursive steps taken by a problem solver in the course of the simulation (Güss, Tuason & Gerhard, 2010).

⁷ Examples are deep vs. shallow processing by Craik & Lockhart, 1972; mindful vs. mindless cognitive activity by Langer, Blank & Chanowitz, 1978; heuristic vs. systematic processing by Chaiken, 1980; central vs. peripheral route by Petty & Cacioppo, 1984; category-based vs. individuating impression formation by Neuberg & Fiske, 1987, among others.

as heuristic, knowledge-based, peripheral and schematic, in contrast to the more effortful systematic, information-based, central, and substantive strategy.

This dual contrast is not without its problems, as the indicators on each side are not featuring one-to-one relationships. Therefore, I need to specify the strategic duality assumed in this study in some more detail. For conflict resolution processes, the decisive distinction is whether persons open up for new information and changes of perspectives, or rather stick to their pre-existing beliefs and refrain from considering new evidence. Closed-minded, knowledge preserving processing is less capacity-demanding than open, information-based processing (Bless, Schwarz, Clore, Golisano, Rabe, & Wölk, 1996). In the following, I will term the more effortful conflict resolution mode *open* processing, as opposed to the less effortful *closed* processing. See Table 1 for a summary. Open and closed conflict resolution styles are understood as poles of a continuum instead of parallel processes (on that distinction see Chaiken, 1980).

When processing closed-mindedly, persons rely on pre-existing knowledge structures like target-specific stereotypes or past experiences (Bless, 2000). These knowledge structures have been subsumed under the generic term “schemata” (e.g., Bless et al., 1996; Chaiken, 1980). Although the schema concept has been criticized for its terminological ambiguity (Alba & Hasher, 1983), it is well-established and thus used in this paper. Schema is understood in its broadest sense as an “active organization of past experiences” (Bartlett, 1932, p. 201) and “organized knowledge about a given concept or type of stimulus” (Janoff-Bulman, 2002, p. 28). Schemata are the basis for shortcuts and simplifications (heuristics) which characterize less effortful processing. Not all information provided needs to be considered but a few context cues suffice for heuristic decision-making. Such judgments based on only a few external cues turned out to be less complex and more extreme (Paulhus & Lim, 1994). The less effortful, closed processing preserves existing knowledge structures and beliefs (Klein & Webster, 2000). In the words of Langer, Chanowitz and Blank: “Mindless behavior is rigidly dictated by the past. Therefore, much of the on-going present situation is hypothesized to go unexamined” (1985, p. 605).

On the other hand, in the open, capacity-demanding conflict resolution style, the available information is scrutinized systematically and novel information is thoroughly selected, learned and interpreted (e.g., Bless, 2000; Chaiken, 1980; Forgas, 1995). Open

thinkers alter existing knowledge-structures in response to new information. They decide carefully, after considering situational details in an effort to avoid mistakes or premature judgments (Celsi & Olson, 1988; Petty, Cacioppo, & Schumann, 1983). The distinction between the open and the closed strategy shares its fundamental characteristics with most of the other dual strategy approaches in the field⁸. To distinguish an information-driven from a knowledge-based strategy proved apt in previous studies on Complex Problem Solving (Otto & Lantermann, 2004; Spring, Wagener, & Funke, 2005). Moreover, DeDreu et al. found that this fundamental distinction generalizes to conflict resolution and negotiation (e.g., DeDreu, Koole, & Oldersma, 1999; DeDreu, Koole, & Steinel, 2000).

Table 1

Characteristics of the open and closed conflict resolution strategy

Open strategy	Closed strategy
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Focus on external stimuli and information provided ○ Effort to validly assess details of the situation before decision-making ○ Integration of new information in existing knowledge structures 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Reliance on internal pre-existing knowledge structures ○ Use of shortcuts and simplifications ○ Conservation of existing cognitive structures - closed-minded thinking

⁸ Also, Fiedler (2000, 2001b) developed a well-known dual-force model that distinguishes two cognitive styles in Piagetian terms: *assimilation* and *accommodation*. Accommodation parallels open processing as described above. It "(...) means to stick to the facts, not to miss or lose potentially relevant stimuli, and to validly assess an actually given stimulus setting" (Fiedler, 2001a, p. 179). However, it is important to note that assimilation *sensu* Fiedler does not correspond with the concept of closed processing as understood in this paper. Indeed, assimilation implies the use of pre-existing knowledge structures; however, it is creative per definition, generative and active. In Fiedler's words, assimilation refers to "the creative function of active generation, or enriching the stimulus input with inferences based on prior knowledge" (Fiedler, 2000, p. 87). A person applies internal cognitive structures to the environment to reshape external information. The closed style I have defined above is not creative and generative, but schematic and preservative.

Strategy indicators in PeaceMaker can be broadly classified into indicators of structure and content. In the analysis of information processing in political conflicts, the differentiation between structure and content is well established (e.g., Guttieri, Wallace, & Suedfeld, 1995). Indicators of both categories are apt to distinguish an open from a closed conflict resolution mode. An open style should facilitate conflict resolution success, as discussed at the end of this section. Table 2 provides a summary of the indicators.

A) Structure

On a structural level, main alternatives are to either gather information (groups and polls) or to implement actions (security, political or construction). For information collection, the players need to click with the mouse on icons at the bottom of the interface. Windows open that provide information about groups' approval and poll results. The frequency of *information use* and *action implementation* was assessed in five 7-minute time intervals. These periods were sufficiently small to capture changes in the structure of conflict resolution strategy with a high degree of validity. On the other hand, the intervals were large enough to contain data sufficient to describe behavior with a high reliability (for a discussion of optimal measurement intervals see Wirth, 2004). Given very high correlations between minutes 0-7 and 7-14 ($r = .86, p < .01$) as well as 14-21 and 21-28 ($p = .84, p < .01$), I pooled these intervals ex posteriori in order to constrain model complexity. The last 7 minutes were registered separately due to a high proportion of missing data.

Open and closed structure

Action implementation and information access are fundamentally different activities. Actions influence the approval scores that indicate game success. Automatically they are in the focus of attention. Events taking place during the game (e.g. militant attacks) and feedbacks given (e.g. a newspaper article about a lack of safety in Israel) act as cues: They suggest implementing certain actions (e.g. to take actions against militants). Thus, PeaceMaker calls on gamers to focus on actions and its cues simplify their selection. By implementing the suggested interventions, the player does not need to deliberate much and invests minimal cognitive effort.

In contrast, a gamer may also implement actions in order to gather new information about the conflict. The careful observation of action consequences provides valuable insights. However, thorough processing of the information needs time and is only possible when few actions are implemented in a row. A low action frequency is thus categorized as a sign for an information-driven conflict resolution mode, whereas a higher number of actions indicate a closed-minded gamer, who does not reflect on new evidence by having short breaks but goes with the flow of the scenario.

Contrary to actions, the groups and polls information sources are not linked to the scores and their use is not self-evident. The player needs to purposefully direct attention to the information bar below by employing high levels of cognitive control. Only an open-minded conflict solver intending to base decisions on large amounts of the information available will score high in *information use frequency*. To sum up, a high action frequency and low information use frequency indicate closed processing, while a low action frequency and high information frequency are part of an open strategy.

B) Free recall

Information-driven processing implicates the integration of novel information in pre-existing knowledge structures (Forgas, 1995). Incorporating new information firmly in existing cognitive structures corresponds to what Craik and Lockhart (1972) described as *deep processing*. The deeper the processing is, the more resistant the resulting memory trace becomes (for empirical evidence see also Craik & Tulving, 1975). Recall is a correlate of memory trace resistance. Thus, better integration of novel information as assumed for an open strategy should be associated with increased free recall performance.

C) Content

PeaceMaker distinguishes security, political and construction actions. In each of these categories, some actions benefit the Israeli as well as the Palestinian side (non zero-sum, *win-win actions*, e.g., to ask the government to unite for peace), while others satisfy the interests of the Israeli side only (zero-sum, *win-lose actions*, e.g., to intensify curfews for Palestinians). The distinction between win-lose and win-win is common in conflict

research (e.g., Blake & Mouton, 1961; Carnevale & Probst, 1998) and game theory (von Neumann & Morgenstern, 1953).

Actions were categorized as typical win-win, typical win-lose or ambiguous in terms of their effect on the approval scores. Actions with a positive impact on both approval scores were identified as win-win, with a positive effect on only the Israeli approval score as win-lose. Subsequently, actions in each category were scored. Scores ranged from 1 for minimum and 4 for maximum win-win and win-lose character (see Appendix B4 for the categorization and scoring).⁹ For each participant, separate scores for the win-win and win-lose category were calculated. In order to ensure inter-subject comparability, the individual win-lose and win-win scores were set in proportion to the total sum score (win-lose + win-win). Apart from the proportion of win-lose or win-win score, also the counted *number* of win-lose and win-win actions was assessed, again set in proportion to the total number of actions.

Moreover, the PeaceMaker immanent categories of political, security and construction actions were of interest for an assessment of action variability. Following Gonzalez, Kampf, & Martin (under review) I calculated a variability metric through the formula:

$$1 - \left[\left(\left(\frac{TotalC}{Total} - \frac{1}{3} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{TotalS}{Total} - \frac{1}{3} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{TotalP}{Total} - \frac{1}{3} \right)^2 \right) \div \frac{2}{3} \right]$$

TotalC, *TotalS* and *TotalP* refer to the total number of security, political and construction actions. *Total* is the sum of all actions implemented during the game. Consequently, the $Total^{C/S/P}/Total$ fraction represents the proportion of each action type in the total number. The highest variability is given if a gamer implements all three types equally frequent (1/3 of the time), the lowest variability, if only one type is used (3/3). In order to obtain the deviance from the maximal variability, 1/3 is subtracted from each $Total^{C/S/P}/Total$ fraction. If only one action type is chosen, the $Total^{C/S/P}/Total$ fraction is

⁹ Note that the impact of actions varies in dependency on the given situation in the game. Categorizations were thus averaged over a range of possible constellations.

2/3 (3/3-1/3). Consequently, the entire variability metric assumes values between 0 (minimum) and 1 (maximum).

Open and closed content

A tendency towards win-lose suggests the use of general conflict schemata and conflict-specific stereotypes. Conflict schemata are about incompatible interests and irreconcilable positions (Bar-Tal, Kruglanski, & Klar, 1989, cf. paragraph 2.5). Thinking in conflict schemata is rigid and win-lose-minded. Furthermore, typical for the gridlocked Israeli-Palestinian conflict are hardliner and zero-sum stances. The ongoing power of the right-wing party Likud and five years of governance by Netanyahu, known for hawkish policies towards Palestinians, have clearly shaped the image of the Israeli PM. Thus, a tendency towards win-lose likely results when relying on general conflict schemata or Israeli-Palestinian specific stereotypes. In addition, a win-lose orientation is compatible with a confirmation bias or positive test strategy heuristic (Friedrich, 1993, p. 1). The confirmation heuristic implies a closed-minded “seeking of evidence in ways that are partial to existing beliefs” (Nickerson, 1998, p. 1). A gamer relying on conflict schemata or stereotypes (e.g., the stereotype that the Palestinian side is dominated by violent attitudes) might choose rough actions (e.g., missile strikes against militant headquarters), thereby provoking the expected consequences in the scenario (e.g., violent reactions from the Palestinians). Thus, pre-existing cognitive structures are confirmed and there is no need for resources-demanding changes. Put together, a propensity to implement win-lose actions reflects a schematic, closed conflict resolution strategy.

In contrast, a strong propensity to implement win-win actions suggests an open conflict resolution strategy. It shows that participants identify the actions which integrate opposing interests by observing what happens within the game.

The reasoning for action variability is similar to that. Maximal variability suggests the use of a diversity heuristic. Its rule is that the probability of bad decisions decreases with increasing variability (see Ayal & Zakay, 2009). Closed-minded thinkers may rely on this heuristic and make a random selection (implementing all categories equally often corresponds to the discrete uniform distribution of random experiments – each category is equally likely to be observed), thereby successfully avoiding to observe the game and to

reflect in every single instance which of the categories would be most appropriate given the current situation. By not adapting their choices to the external circumstances, they are approximating the maximal variability (1/3 of the actions taken from each category) more closely than open-minded thinkers do. To recap, high variability, together with more win-lose actions are indicators of a more closed-minded conflict resolution mode.

D) Success

Different parameters were used in order to determine how successful a gamer was in managing the Israeli-Palestinian conflict.

1) *Number of lost games (NLOS)*. The most straightforward measure was the number of games lost. Each participant played at least for 28 minutes. After the 28th minute, there was no further trial. Hence, this dependent variable referred to the number of *game over* in the 28 minutes time span.

2) *Time of first game (TIM1)*. I also expected it to be insightful how long someone could successfully maintain the position of the Israeli Prime Minister in the first trial. TIM1 was scaled in seconds.

3) *Overall time (TIMT)*. Since after the 28th minute no new game was started, the total duration of involvement in the scenario varied with gaming success. The longer a participant played, the better her control of the scenario was. TIMT was assessed in seconds as well.

4) *Difference score (BIAS)*. Successful conflict resolution behavior means to reconcile the interests of both sides. However, the realistic scenario triggers some identification with the assigned role of the Israeli Prime Minister, resulting in a focus on Israeli interests and a higher Israeli approval score. For instance, in a PeaceMaker study by Gonzalez and Martin (2010) all participants independent from original affiliation with the conflict parties favored the Israeli side in their role as Israeli PM. In order to calculate the BIAS metric, the Palestinian score was subtracted from the Israeli approval score. A small BIAS (small approval score difference) indicated successful conflict resolution behavior - the gamer managed to gain the approval of both sides. On the other side, a high BIAS meant that interests of the "own" Israeli side were overrepresented and the

Israeli score manifestly exceeded the Palestinian score. Hence, conflict resolution success was low.

5) *Cumulative success score (CORE)*. To economize in later regression analysis, I calculated a score that combined average Israeli and Palestinian approval scores, number of games lost and time of gaming in one dependent measure with the following formula:

$$\frac{\text{Mean}(\text{Balance Game}_1, \text{Balance Game}_2 \dots \text{Balance Game}_n) - \frac{NLOS}{TIMT}}{100}$$

Balance was calculated following Gonzalez and Czlonka (in press):

$$\frac{1 - [(95 - \text{Israeli Approval Game}_n) + (100 - \text{Palestinian Approval Game}_n)]}{342}$$

Balance assessed how close the gamer was to a two-state-solution. In this study, the maximal approval value was 95 points on the Israeli, and 100 points on the Palestinian side, reached by only one person winning the game. Thus, these scores were set as the upper threshold. Minimum values observed in this sample were -67 for the Israeli approval and -80 for the Palestinian approval. Consequently the maximal range of scores in this study was 342 (100+95+80+67). *Balance* assumed values between 0 for the worst player and 1 for the one who achieved a two-state-solution. Because many players lost and started a new game, the balance scores of the trials were averaged.

Since gaming success was not exhaustively expressed in the approval scores, the *balance* average score was reduced by the ratio of *NLOS* and *TIMT*, i.e. games lost and seconds of gaming accumulated for all attempts. Many lost games in a short time period indicated low conflict resolution success. The more *game over* and the fewer seconds played, the larger the reduction of average *balance* was. If the gamer did not lose at all, the fraction assumed a value of zero and the *balance* average score was not reduced. To put *CORE* in a nutshell; *the lower the two approval scores were, the more games lost and the shorter the time span until each game over, the worse the overall gaming performance and the smaller CORE was.* Values ranged between -.14 and 1.00.

Success and an open or closed strategy

A closed-minded conflict resolution strategy should obstruct conflict resolution success; an open strategy should facilitate it. Also, CPS research suggests that an information-based strategy may be advantageous in an exploratory stage of problem solving as given in this study (Vollmeyer, Burns, & Holyoak, 1996). Research on negotiation and mediation in real-world conflicts revealed that a (closed-minded) reliance on focal points and stereotypes hampered the negotiation progress (De Dreu, Koole, & Oldersma, 1999). However, every novice PeaceMaker player faces difficulties (Gonzalez & Czlodka, in press; Gonzalez, Czlodka, & Eisenberg, under review). This is intended by the game's developers Asi Burak and Eric Brown. As Burak puts it: "Part of that losing is part of the lesson, you know, to see that frustration and lack of control that you have (...) You can't win in five minutes something, you know, 60 years is" (NPR, 2007). Thus, floor effects are likely, but nevertheless, I expected closed-mindedness to hamper conflict resolution for good reasons;

Structure (actions and information)

To gather information about the support of different stakeholders (*groups*) and about changes in conflict-related polling variables (*polls*) should facilitate good decisions. Also, a low action frequency, which allows the collection of information on the impact of actions, is assumed to influence gaming success positively. Closed-minded gamers do the contrary and should not advance conflict resolution much.

Content (win-lose and action variability)

The gamers depend on the trust of both sides. As Asi Burak said: "You know, you have to take care of the other side, I mean, it's very important in PeaceMaker. You can't just make your people satisfied and win the game" (NPR, 2007). Like in real world conflicts, conflict resolution progress is achieved through a non zero-sum, win-win approach. Thus, the more win-lose actions the closed-minded problem solvers implement, the lower their game success should become. The expected high action variability of closed-minded thinkers is an indicator for a random selection of actions, and accordingly just as little beneficial for conflict resolution progress.

Table 2

Indicators of an open and closed strategy

	Open strategy	Closed strategy
Structure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Much information used ○ Low number of actions implemented 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Little information used ○ High number of actions implemented
Recall	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Much information recalled 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Little information recalled
Content	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Few win-lose actions as compared to win-win actions (high win-win preponderance) ○ Low action variability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Many win-lose actions as compared to win-win actions (low win-lose preponderance) ○ High action variability
Success	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Successful 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Unsuccessful

2.4 THE CONCEPT OF AFFECT

Identity association, I suppose, is associated with closed-minded conflict resolution, and that should be at least partially explainable by affect. Affect is an important variable because issues related to the self (e.g., due to identity association) cause stronger affective responses (Epstein, 1973; Iyer & Leach, 2008; Lazarus, 2001; Lazarus & Folkman, 1984; Rogers, 1951).

Affect as a generic term comprises phenomena like mood, emotions, emotional episodes or stress responses (Scherer, 1984; for a discussion on definitions, readers are referred to Beedie, Terry, & Lane, 2005; Oatley & Jenkins, 1996; Russell 1996). Studies of self-reported feelings, affect-related words or facial expressions suggest that consciously accessible affective feelings can be described in terms of their valence (pleasure) and arousal (activation) quality (Russell & Barrett, 1999; Russell 2005). The valence dimension refers to a hedonic tone that varies between the opposite poles of unpleasantness and pleasantness. Arousal is a non-specific energizing force, a “general drive state (...), an energizer, but not a guide; an engine but not a steering gear” (Hebb, 1955, p. 249). Like valence, it is said to occur on “a continuum, from a low point during deep sleep to a high point during extreme effort or great excitement” (Duffy, 1957, p. 267). In the realization of a certain conscious feeling, pleasure and arousal are merged (e.g., Barrett, 1998; Kuppens, 2007). For instance, persons may feel tense, stressed or nervous, when simultaneously given high levels of activation and unpleasantness.

In their *affect circumplex model* (shown in Appendix A1), Russell and Barrett construe activation and valence as orthogonal, bipolar dimensions (e.g., Barrett & Russell 1999; Russell, 2005). However, the scholars agree with others in the field that valence and arousal are interrelated dimensions (Barrett & Wager, 2006; Watson, Clark, Weber, Assenheimer, Strauss, & McCormick, 1995). The structure of affect is a highly controversial topic. However, the dimensions of valence and arousal have proven to reliably assess the emotional experience and are therefore suited for the current research purpose.

2.5 MAIN HYPOTHESES: REASONS FOR A CLOSED CONFLICT RESOLUTION MODE

In most highly complex and unusual situations such as the PeaceMaker game, persons invest a cognitive effort in order to be able to manage the task (e.g., Forgas, 1992).¹⁰ However, identity association, I suppose, makes participants eschew from an effortful, information-based processing strategy. Different lines of research substantiate this expectation. Note, that the following presentation aims to provide an overview over possible mechanisms. Only a subset of variables can be tested in this study.

The conflict situation is more important for high than for low identity associated persons. Identity association implies *commitments* (Boninger, Krosnick, & Berent, 1995). In the words of Lazarus, commitments are “reflections of and brought together under what personality psychology treats as the self (...)” (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984, p. 79), “they express what is important to the person (...), they determine what is at stake in a specific stressful encounter” (Ibid, p. 56). The commitments of identity-associated persons may lead to closed processing. Langer understood cognitive commitments as “(...) frozen or rigidly held beliefs that unwittingly are unmodulated by context” (Langer, 1994, p. 34). “One freezes the meaning of information, (...) is unaware of alternative conceptions, [and] is unlikely to scrutinize information” (Ibid, p. 39). Similarly, Johnson

¹⁰ However, elaborate, effortful thinking is not necessarily the best strategy for accomplishing complex tasks, cf. Dijksterhuis, 2004.

and Eagly concluded in their meta-analysis on persuasion that value-based involved subjects “must have engaged in relatively closed-minded processing” (Johnson & Eagly, 1989, p. 310), since they were less persuaded with increasing value-commitment no matter the strength of the arguments.

In previous studies, value-based commitment was related to biased (Pomerantz, Chaiken, & Tordesillas, 1995) or reduced information processing (Maio & Olson, 1995; Sherif, Kelly, Rodgers, Sarup, & Tittler, 1973). In a Complex Problem Solving task, high value-involved subjects considered the information provided more superficially as compared to subjects in a low value-involvement condition (Illies & Reiter-Palmon, 2004). Reliance on existing schemata and disregard for new information may thus be readily explainable by persons’ cognitive commitments

The cognitive commitments of identity-associated participants should also be consequential for their affective experience. Commitments are said to increase the likelihood of stress appraisals (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984).

2.5.1 *Cognitive appraisals*

A stress appraisal would be the most natural reaction to PeaceMaker (according to the features of stress inducing situations, Lazarus & Folkman, 1984). Like in real-world conflicts, time pressure and imminence is high; the scenario is complex, ambiguous, evaluative and highly demanding. Besides, it is prone to evoke stress due to modeling a tense conflict on behalf of threatening music and images or videos taken from real news reports which contain a considerable degree of violence (on the relation between conflict and stress see Holsti, 1990; Steigleder, Weiss, Balling, Wenninger, & Lombardo, 1980). When a person feels able to cope with the demands of the stress situation, a challenge appraisal occurs (Blascovich & Mendes, 2000). Initially, the performance situation in Peacemaker should appear benign, controllable, and thus *challenging*. Challenge is characterized by high arousal and positive valence (in terms of discrete emotions: eagerness, excitement and exhilaration; Lazarus & Folkman, 1984). Appraisal occurs continuously (Smith & Kirby, 2001). After some gaming, participants should become aware that PeaceMaker is highly difficult to control. A feeling of low certainty (i.e.

participants feel barely able to predict the development of game variables) and competence (or control) ensues. Dörner identified low levels of certainty and competence as main antecedents of threat appraisals (Dörner, Kreuzig, Reither, & Stäudel, 1994; Dörner, 2002; Dörner, Gerdes, & Hagg, 2008). Thus, the challenge appraisal is expected to turn into a threat appraisal, which is characterized by high arousal and negative valence (fear, anxiety, anger). This pattern should be observable in all participants.

However, as commitments increase stress appraisals (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984), high identity-associated persons are assumed to initially appraise the conflict situation as *more* challenging and later as *more* threatening than low identity-associated ones. In terms of affect, this means (1) a stronger positive valence at the beginning which subsequently turns into a stronger negative valence and (2) higher arousal during the whole game for the high identity-associated group. The affective reaction is induced by the conflict scenario itself and corresponds to what Mellers et al. called task-related emotions (Mellers, Erev, Fessler, Hemelrijk, Hertwik, & Laland, 2001).

Social psychological research generated a large body of models that aim to explain how and when affect influences processing strategies (for a review see Fiedler, 2001a). However, by exclusively looking at the effects of affective *valence* on cognition, they failed to address the arousal dimension of the emotional experience, which is integral to the well-known models of affect (Barrett, 1998; Russell, 2005; Watson et al., 1995). The mood-induction procedures used in these studies (e.g., music, movies) are not without impact on arousal. Thus, differences found in processing strategy could likewise be due to differences in arousal instead of or in addition to affective valence. This study avoids confounding by explicitly assessing arousal (2.5.3) next to valence (2.5.2).

2.5.2 Valence

High identity-associated participants are expected to experience more positive affect at the beginning and more negative affect later in the game, as compared to low-identity associated ones. In other words, they should feel a pronounced drop in pleasure. A strong change in affect may deplete working memory resources, reflected in less resource-demanding, closed processing (Ellis & Ashbrook, 1988; Isen, 1987; Mackie &

Worth, 1989). Ellis and Ashbrook's (1988) resource allocation model, based on theories of capacity by Kahneman (1973) or Kerr (1973), assumes negative and positive affect to cause interferences in the form of intrusive or task-irrelevant thoughts that affect working memory capacity. Due to the depleted capacity, persons pay less attention to relevant features of a given task and may base their decisions instead on well-established schemata.

Although some studies found low-effort processing in a positive mood condition (Ellis, Seibert, & Varner, 1995; Mackie & Worth, 1989), the literature in the field predominately suggests that positive affect does not deplete working memory capacity (Bless et al., 1996; Derakshan & Eysenck, 2010). Happy participants consistently showed better performance in creativity and problem-solving tasks (Isen, 2001; Isen, Daubman, & Nowicki, 1987).

By contrast, studies which induced negative affect provide considerable support for Ellis and Ashbrook's model. Negative mood was associated with worse text comprehension (Ellis, Ottaway, Varner, Becker, & Moore, 1997) and poorer recall (Seibert & Ellis, 1991). In addition, persons with a comparatively better ability to regulate negative affect showed less systematic and less detail-oriented processing in a Complex Problem Solving scenario (Otto & Lantermann, 2004). Possibly, the cognitive capacity used for affect regulation has been withdrawing resources from the task. Reduced resource allocation after the induction of negative affect was also observable psychophysiologicaly in event-related brain potentials (Kliegel, Horn, & Zimmer, 2003). In a recent review, Derakshan and Eysenck (2010) reported on reasonable agreement in the field that negative emotions affect the central executive of working memory. They concluded that "the adverse effects associated with negative emotional states may well depend in part on negative task-irrelevant processing, for example, rumination in the case of depression and worry in the case of anxiety" (Derakshan & Eysenck, 2010, p. 196). Distractive thoughts are particularly likely in case of changes in valence, since changes draw persons' attention and make them reflect on their affective states. Thus, engaging in task-irrelevant processing, high identity-associated participants may lack the resources to adopt an open, information-driven strategy and rather close their minds.

2.5.3 *Arousal*

Also, high arousal levels are associated with depleted processing capacity. For instance, Humphreys and Revelle (1984) reviewed evidence suggesting that high arousal reduced the resources available for retention processes over short time intervals, thereby impairing performance in high-load tasks. Playing PeaceMaker, this would mean less informational details provided by the game being kept in the focal memory so that participants need to rely on their pre-existing schemata instead. Kahneman (1973) made similar predictions. Specifically, he assumed high arousal to cause “narrowing of attention, increased lability of attention, difficulties in controlling attention by fine discriminations and systematic changes of strategy in various tasks” (1973, p. 42). This corresponds to Easterbrook’s (1959) argument that in states of high arousal only a few cues are used - not compatible with open processing where people try to assess all the environmental information validly. With his model, Easterbrook aimed to substantiate Hebb (1955), who famously claimed the impact of arousal levels on cognitive performance to follow an inverted U-function. In sum, these models indicate that high arousal is detrimental to a processing style which considers a broad range of information and integrates this information in existing cognitive structures.

Dörner put special emphasis on the inhibitory effects of arousal on cortical memory processes (Dörner, 2002; Dörner et al., 2008). Neuroscience has shown that top-down and bottom-up controlled neuronal inhibition influences information representation and processing (for a review, see Knudsen, 2007). High arousal levels are assumed to correspond with a high activity of inhibitory neurons in cortical networks, wherefore cell-to-cell communication is reduced and only strong, well-consolidated associations become activated (see Pinel, 2001). Thus, persons rely on schemata and other frequently reinforced information when having high arousal levels and refrain from careful, time-consuming information collection (Dörner, 2002; Dörner, Gerdes, & Hagg, 2008).

Considerable evidence supports the idea that high arousal evokes a closed processing style. Kim and Baron found increased reliance on stereotypic information when arousal was high (1988). In a study by Sanbonmatsu and Kardes (1988), attitudes of

highly aroused participants were significantly more influenced by peripheral cues than attitudes of a moderate arousal group. In a study by Paulhus and Lim (1994), high arousal was associated with reduced cognitive complexity and a polarization in the evaluation of celebrities. The researchers concluded that “the distinction between [our] high and low arousal conditions would be explained by a qualitative switch from analytic (substantive, controlled) to heuristic (automatic, peripheral, schematic) strategies” (p. 97). Arousal’s relationship with processing mode is also suggested by research on specific emotions. Lerner, Goldberg and Tetlock (1998) demonstrated that feeling angry was related to cognitive simplification as expressed in a narrowed cue utilization. Anger is marked by negative valence and heightened arousal (Levenson, Ekman, & Friesen, 1990).

2.5.4 Motivation for closure

Kruglanski found reduced cognitive capacity to evoke a motivation towards closure (Kruglanski, 2004; Kossowska, 2006). Cognitive closure is “the desire for a definite answer on some topic, any answer as opposed to confusion and ambiguity” (Kruglanski, 1989, p. 114). In their motivation for closure, persons “seize” on pre-existing judgmental cues and “freeze” pre-existing beliefs instead of elaborately processing new information (Kruglanski & Webster, 1996). They rely on stereotypes and schemata, show in-group biases and less assimilation of new information into existing knowledge structures (for an overview see Kruglanski, 2004). For instance, the high need of closure participants in a persuasion study by Klein and Webster (2000) used heuristic cues, while persons in low need of closure processed information systematically. DeDreu, Koole and Oldersma (1999) showed a relationship between high motivation for cognitive closure and reliance on past experiences and stereotypes in negotiation. Thus, not only depleted capacity itself, but also its impact on motivation may lead to closed-mindedness.

2.5.5 Threat appraisals: Valence and arousal embedded

High identity-associated participants are expected to react with threat appraisals after some gaming in PeaceMaker. Both conflict and CPS research have addressed threat

effects. Particularly comprehensive are the models developed by Holsti for international conflict research (Holsti, 1990; the model is illustrated in Appendix A2) and Dörner in the CPS domain (Dörner, 2002).

Holsti assumed that conflicts evoke threat appraisals especially when important values are at stake, as given for identity association with the conflict. Threat, he suggested, reduces the span of attention and increases cognitive rigidity. This should result in selective filtering of information, reliance on past experience, importance of existing cognitive schemata, stereotyping, importance of short-run values, a reduced sensitivity to the perspective of the other party, less resistance to the need for cognitive closure and a decrease in cue awareness as well as reduced intolerance of ambiguity. Decisions are therefore based on less information and less analysis of alternatives and their consequences. These processing consequences of threat defined by Holsti for international conflicts perfectly parallel a closed processing mode.

Closed processing is also what characterizes an “intellectual emergency reaction” (IER), as identified by Dörner in CPS research (Dörner, 1981, p. 167; Dörner et al., 1994, p. 426ff). The IER is a fast, general reaction to threat appraisals. External environmental stimuli determine behavior instead of internal analytic activities (externalization of behavior control). Decisions are accordingly fast. A PeaceMaker player experiencing an IER implements the interventions cued by the scenario without much action planning and omits to access the information sources because this requires a planned intention. Part of an IER is also not to reflect about long-term consequences of actions; in PeaceMaker, it is a high action frequency which indicates that participants do not pause to deliberate on consequences. Moreover, persons in an IER tend to ad-hoc-actions, directed at singular, independent goals. For instance, they may focus on the approval of only one side in the conflict (singular goal) instead of aiming to reconcile interests of both sides (general goal); consequences of this are a high proportion of win-lose actions, a high bias towards one side, and, finally, low gaming success. Moreover, in an IER, new information is not integrated in pre-existing knowledge structures. Apparently, these specifics of an IER defined by Dörner match a closed processing mode very well.

Supporting these models, already moderate threat perceptions have been shown to lead to narrow cognitive categories (Mikulincer & Sheffi, 2000) and reduced cognitive

flexibility (Carnevale & Probst, 1998). Also, applied conflict research has demonstrated that threat results in closed-minded thinking. In the scope of their research on integrative complexity, Suedfeld et al. found that war or other highly threatening solutions to national crises were related to more “simplicity” of political decision-makers (Suedfeld, Tetlock, & Ramirez, 1977; Guttieri, Wallace, & Suedfeld, 1995). Simplicity is marked by rigidity, restricted information use and gross distinctions. In contrast, no decrease in complexity was found for non-violent (i.e., not so threatening) crises. Of special interest to this study, Suedfeld et al. revealed reduced complexity of decision-makers in tense periods of the Israeli-Palestinian conflict. It goes without saying that a computer scenario cannot be as threatening as real world conflicts. However, already mild threat appraisals can result in closed-mindedness (Dörner et al., 1994, p. 427).

2.5.6 *Conflict schemata*

Identity-associated persons are expected to rely on conflict schemata. What, then, do these schemata look like? Conflict means the *perception* of the incompatibility of goals and a mutual or unilateral interference in the goal achievement efforts of the other party or parties (Hammer, 2001, p. 60). Correspondingly, Bar-Tal, Kruglanski and Klar (1989) identified the belief in an incompatibility of goals as the core element of a general conflict schema. Bar-Tal et al. predict a conflict schema to be highly accessible if (1) a conflict context is *expected* and if (2) the conflict schema is related to motivational factors like *values*: “The salience of values keeps a specific conflict schema in the forefront of the cognitive repertoire” (Bar-Tal, Kruglanski, & Klar, 1989, p. 249). Both should be true for high identity-associated participants. Their expectations, I suppose, are more conflict-focused as compared to low identity-associated participants since they are more aware of the severeness of the situation in Israel-Palestine; they are “closer” to the conflict and the conflict content of the game is more meaningful to them. The second condition of schema accessibility is satisfied by the *value-involvement* facet of identity association. Value-based involvement means that the conflict schema is related to values. Hence, a conflict mental set should be very accessible to high identity-associated participants.

Empirical evidence suggests that the activation of conflict schemata relates to a closed processing style: “The conflict mental set corresponds to the concepts of rigid thinking and black-white thinking” (Carnevale & Probst, 1998, p. 1300). Subjects anticipating or experiencing a conflict situation, compared with persons anticipating or experiencing cooperative contexts, disregarded information about connections among issues (Carnevale & Pruitt, 1992), showed less complex thinking in cognitive tasks (Carnevale & Probst, 1998) and focused more strongly on dissimilarities and incompatibilities in opinions (Judd, 1978). Note that a focus on incompatibilities finds expression in an increased amount of *win-lose actions* with unilateral benefits.

Finally, analyses of real-world decision-making corroborate the relationship between conflict and closed-mindedness. Lebow (1981) and Snyder and Diesing (1977) studied an ample range of conflicts. They reported on frequent stereotyping and premature judgments about reactions of the opponent, lack of search for alternatives and substandard evaluation of action consequences. In 16 crises observed by Snyder and Diesing, only 40% of the information exchanged between governments was understood correctly.

To recap the different reasons for closed-mindedness of identity-associated persons: Identity association implies cognitive commitments which by themselves may have a freezing impact on information processing. Moreover, they increase stress appraisals and accordingly elicit stronger affective responses to the conflict scenario. Affect depletes working memory capacity, which may result in closed processing in its own right and by raising persons’ motivation for closure. Due to all this (and possibly more), identity-associated participants should show a closed-minded conflict resolution style.

The main hypotheses of this study are the following:

Main hypotheses

- H1. The conflict resolution strategy of high identity-associated participants is more closed-minded than the strategy of low identity-associated participants.
- H2. High identity-associated participants show a stronger decrease in affective valence and higher arousal levels than low-identity associated participants. Valence and arousal mediate the relationship between identity involvement and conflict resolution strategy.

Figure 6. Generic mediation model being tested (on the basis of Baron & Kenny, 1986).

2.5.7 A special issue: Effects of affiliation with a conflict party

The reliance on conflict schemata and conflict-specific stereotypes, as typical for a closed-minded conflict resolution mode, implies a tendency towards a win-lose stance and thus a high bias metric (expressing favoritism for the Israeli side). Both Israel- and Palestine- affiliated participants are identity-associated and are therefore assumed to show a high bias. However, in a study by Gonzalez and Martin (2010), Palestine-affiliated

even more than Israel-affiliated participants showed such a bias. I expect to replicate this finding, since it is explainable in terms of a closed processing mode.

The “naïve realism” approach postulates that beliefs of partisans involved in social-political conflicts overestimate the extremity of the other side’s stance (Robinson, Keltner, Ward, & Ross, 1995; see also Gonzalez & Martin, 2010, p. 19). Thus, in the belief structure of Palestine-affiliated participants, a prototypical Israeli leader is more hawkish and win-lose orientated than in the belief structure of Israel-affiliated participants. If all identity-associated participants follow their pre-existing cognitive structures (e.g., stereotypes), then - according to “naïve realism” - the Palestine-affiliated ones pick the most extreme win-lose measures with the clearest unilateral benefits for the Israeli side and therefore have the highest bias scores.

2.6 CONTROL VARIABLES

Identity association with the Israeli-Palestinian conflict goes along with more *knowledge* about the topic. High identity-associated participants are expected to rely on their pre-existing cognitive structures, to which conflict-specific knowledge belongs. Thus, performance may not only differ due to reliance on schemata, heuristics and stereotypes, but also due to the use of specific knowledge. It is included as control variable in order to disentangle these effects. Knowledge has been shown to influence Complex Problem Solving (e.g., Frensch & Funke, 1995), information processing (Maheswaran & Sternthal, 1990) and information search (Srinivasan & Ratchford, 1991). Most relevant for this study, recent research with PeaceMaker revealed the significance of knowledge about the conflict for conflict resolution strategies (Gonzalez, Czlönka & Eisenberg, under review; Gonzalez, Kampf & Martin, under review).

Moreover, owing to their familiarity with the topic, high identity-associated participants may *feel more in control* over the scenario, which could also impact conflict resolution strategies. Since I was primarily interested in the influence of affect and arousal, feelings of control were included as control variable, assessed as “fear of failure” (Questionnaire on Current Motivation by Rheinberg, Vollmeyer, & Burns, 2001) and “dominance” (dominance scale of the Self-Assessment Manikin, Bradley, & Lang, 1994).

Past research with computer simulations indicates that gaming experience must be controlled for (e.g., Donchin, 1995; Gonzalez & Martin, 2010). Since PeaceMaker is a game in English but the sample consisted of German students, it was necessary to control for English proficiency. Last but not least, although it is still unclear whether Complex Problem Solving is related to global intelligence (cf. Wenke, Frensch, & Funke, 2005), intelligence could have had an impact on conflict resolution ability. The final school grade was included as a proxy of intelligence because various studies proved high correlations between grades and classical IQ tests (e.g., Laidra, Pullmann, & Allik, 2007).

3 METHOD

I will first describe how the different variables of interest in this study were assessed (3.1). Subsequently, sample and procedure are presented (3.2).

3.1 MEASUREMENT

Measures are subdivided into identity variables (3.1.1), mediators (3.1.2), control variables (3.1.3) and items administered subsequent to the computer scenario (3.1.4). I further assessed the personality variable dogmatism, but its presentation is beyond the scope of this paper. All questionnaires were in German language.

3.1.1 Identity variables

Religion. Participants indicated whether they belonged to Christianity, Islam, Buddhism, Hinduism, Judaism, no religion or a religion not listed. It was further distinguished whether their religion was highly conflict-associated (Muslim and Jewish) or lowly conflict-associated (Christian, none and other religion). For regression analyses, conflict relevance was dummy coded (1 = highly relevant; 0 = lowly relevant).

Geo-cultural origin. This identity variable was defined by a participant's birthplace and the parents' nationality. When the parents came from different geo-cultural regions, only the birthplace was considered. This applied in one case. Geo-cultural regions were distinguished following the second level of the United Nations categorization (United Nations, 2005, see the categorization reproduced in Appendix B1). As additional group variable, I categorized whether participants came either from Western Asia or a region not affected by the conflict. In regression analyses, Western Asia was coded as 1 (region affected by the conflict), the other origins as 0 (regions not affected).

Affiliation to the conflict parties. A 5-item self-report questionnaire assessed the extent to which participants considered themselves associated with the conflict parties. Participants answered items on a bipolar 7-point scale. One pole (-3) of the scale represented the Israeli, the other pole (+3) the Palestinian side of the conflict, the middle (0) indicated neutrality. An example item is: "I have a stronger relationship with (...)". See

Appendix C1 for the whole questionnaire. Item discrimination ranged from .89 to .92. The scale was used to build the categorical variable *affiliation*. Since internal consistency of the scale proved very high ($\alpha = .97$), I used an additive index for the categorization of participants. Those having an additive Index with values between -5 and -15 were grouped as Israel-affiliated ($n = 47$), participants with values between +5 and +15 as Palestine-affiliated ($n = 47$). The group in between did not show a clear affiliation and was thus coded as non-affiliated ($n = 30$).

Value-involvement in the conflict. Johnson & Eagly (1989) distinguished value-based involvement from impression-relevant and outcome-relevant involvement. Cho and Boster's (2005) questionnaire assessing these three dimensions of involvement showed good discriminant validity of the respective subscales (Cho & Boster, 2005; Illies & Reiter-Palmon, 2004; Marshall & Reinhart, 2008). I used Cho and Boster's items on value-involvement with a 5-point Likert scale ranging from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree". An example is: "The values that are the most important to me are what determines my stand on the Israeli-Palestinian conflict" (see Appendix C1 for the whole questionnaire). Cronbach's alpha was satisfying ($\alpha = .81$). The range of item discrimination varied between .47 and .64.

3.1.2 Mediators

Valence and Arousal. I deployed the Self-Assessment Manikin (SAM, Bradley & Lang, 1994), a well-established pictographic measure of affect used in a multitude of studies (cf. Güntekin, 2007; Nielsen & Krasznik, 2006; Terhaar, Boettger, Schwier, Wagner, Israel, & Bär, 2010). The SAM assesses valence and arousal with two separate sub-scales (see Appendix C2). Arousal has often been measured psychophysically. However, self-report measures are highly correlated with physiological indicators and thus an equally valid way of assessment (Thayer, 1989).

3.1.3 Control variables

Knowledge about the conflict. I developed a pool of multiple-choice items about political and historical facts of the Israeli-Palestinian conflict and according to pretest-results chose the 9 items with the highest item selectivity (see Appendix C1 for the items). Each question had five answer options. An “I don’t know” option was always included to constrain guessing. Difficulty of the test proved medium (Median = 4, M=4.34, SD=2.99).

English proficiency. Following the rating scheme presented in Appendix B2, the number of months the participant had spent in an English speaking country and a self-rating of the adequate English school grade were subsumed to one index (1 for sufficient English proficiency to 5 for excellent English proficiency).

Dominance. The third picture-based scale of the Self-Assessment Manikin measures the dimension of dominance (again, see Appendix C2).

Fear of failure. The Questionnaire on Current Motivation (QCM) by Rheinberg, Vollmeyer, & Burns, 2001) encompasses a factor called “anxiety”, which assesses the fear of failure (Vollmeyer & Rheinberg, 2006, p. 241; see the items of this subscale in Appendix C1). In the QCM, participants rate 18 items on a 7-point Likert scale. Rheinberg et al. postulate the questionnaire to have a 4-factor structure (see Appendix C3). The Eigenvalues obtained through principal component analysis confirmed this structure (first six Eigenvalues: 4.24, 3.57, 1.78, 1.1, 0.99, .90). However, Varimax rotation yielded only two factors with good interpretability and high internal consistency (see the factor loadings in Appendix C3). Factor 1 overlaps with the factor termed “anxiety” by Rheinberg et al. (Items 5, 9, 12, 16, but 14 instead of 18, Cronbach's $\alpha = .84$), factor 2 basically matches the factor “interest” (Items 1, 7, 11, 17, but 13 instead of 4, Cronbach's $\alpha = .81$). The factor “anxiety” expresses the fear of failure and was of principal relevance in this study.

Demographical data. I also inquired gender, age, year of study and academic field (see Appendix B3). These demographical control variables lacked any impact on the study variables.

3.1.4 Follow-up items

Free recall task. Participants were asked to list all the groups and leaders that were present in the *groups* bar and all the indicators contained in the *polls* bar. Only the number of correct recall responses was counted, since false alarms were negligible ($n = 6$). Of course, it was statistically controlled for the number of *groups* and *polls* that had been accessed in the game.

Identification with the role of the Israeli PM. Identification was measured with two items: “I did not identify with role of the Israeli Prime Minister that I assumed in the game” and “My identification with the position of the Prime Minister was high”. Answers were given on a 7-point Likert scale (“strongly disagree” to “strongly agree”; see Appendix C1).

3.2 PARTICIPANTS AND PROCEDURE

124 Participants (as many males as females) between 18 and 33 years ($M = 23.62$, $SD = 3.87$) were recruited at different faculties of the University of Heidelberg and via a social network in the internet („studivZ“). A monetary compensation was offered. All were students or had completed a university degree in different academic fields, with a majority in psychology (41.1%; see Appendix B3 for the different areas of studies). 54.1% of the participants indicated Christian religion, 12.9% Jewish religion, 12.1% Muslim religion, 19.3% did not belong to a religious group, the religion of 1.6% was not specified (see Figure 7 for the absolute number of participants in each category). In total, 31 belonged to a group with a highly conflict-associated religion (Muslim and Jewish) and 93 to a group with a lowly conflict relevant religion (other). Participants originated from Western Europe, Eastern Europe, Western Asia and the United States. 22 had a geo-cultural origin in Western Asia, the region broadly affected by the conflict. 8 participants were born in the central conflict region of Israel-Palestine itself. In total, 31.5% of the participants were not born in Western Europe or had at least one parent with a non Western European nationality (10.5%: origin in Eastern Europe, 3.2%: US, 17.8%: Western Asia with 6.5 % of them in Israel-Palestine; see Figure 7 for the absolute number in each category).

Figure 7. Number of participants with regard to religion and origin.

With $M = 1.31$, $SD = 3.72$ gaming hours per week, the affinity to computer gaming was low. Knowledge about the conflict proved average ($M = 4.34$ out of 9 answers correct, $SD = 2.99$). English proficiency was good (self-rated school grade: $M = 1.94$, $SD = 0.78$; months spent in an English speaking country: $M = 11.10$, $SD = 33.63$; overall proficiency score: $M = 3.21$, $SD = 1.32$).

The collection of data took place at the University of Heidelberg and followed three stages. *Stage 1*: Participants signed the consent form. Then, the first serial of questionnaires was administered, with items concerning religion, geo-cultural origin, English proficiency, school grade, gaming hours, affiliation to the conflict parties, value-based involvement in the conflict, knowledge about the conflict and dogmatism (not discussed in this paper). *Stage 2*: In order to learn how to control the Complex Problem solving scenario, participants went through a written tutorial and simultaneously tested the functions in the computer simulation. Afterwards, they completed the Questionnaire on Current Motivation and the Self-Assessment Manikin for the first measurement of arousal, valence and dominance. A minimal gaming time of 28 minutes was scheduled, i.e., in case of a game over before the 28th minute, a new trial was started. However, 4 participants had to quit before due to technical malfunctioning. Therefore, minimal gaming time recorded was 19 minutes; the maximum were 41 minutes. After 10 and 20 minutes of conflict resolution, participants were shortly interrupted to complete the Self-Assessment Manikin. *Stage 3*: Subsequently to finishing the complex problem solving scenario, another questionnaire was administered assessing recall and identification with the role of the Israeli Prime Minister.

4 RESULTS

I will first provide descriptive data on conflict resolution strategy (4.1), as well as on control variables, identity variables and their relationship (4.2). Afterwards, the main hypotheses H1 (4.3) and H2 (4.4) are addressed: Is identity association related to a closed-minded conflict resolution strategy? And, if this is the case, does affect mediate this relationship?

4.1 CONFLICT RESOLUTION IN THE TOTAL SAMPLE

Which strategy was predominantly pursued in the conflict simulation? How are indicators of open and closed strategy interrelated? Which indicators predict conflict resolution success?

4.1.1 *Descriptive results for the conflict resolution strategy*

A) Structure

Overall, the trend went from an information-oriented to an action-oriented strategy (see Table 3). Comparing the two main intervals, in the first half players viewed nearly as many *groups and polls* ($M = 11.6$) as they chose *actions* ($M = 13.1$). In the second half, the proportion of *actions* ($M = 18.1$) was clearly higher than the information accessed ($M = 7.5$). T-tests confirmed that gamers attended to considerably more *groups* ($M = 8.1$ vs. 4.6 ; $t = 3.36$; $p = .001$)¹¹ and *polls* ($M = 3.5$ vs. 2.5 ; $t = 1.79$; $p = .08$) in interval I than in interval II. The contrary was true for actions. The number of actions chosen was significantly higher in the second half than in the first half ($M = 13.1$ vs. 18.5 , $t = -10.33$, $p = .00$). All participants used very few *polls*, resulting in a restricted range. Since this made floor effects very likely, later regression analyses were focused on the *groups*.

¹¹ The normal distribution assumption of all variables was tested with the Shapiro-Wilk and Kolmogorov-Smirnoff-Lilliefors-Test.

Table 3

Means and standard deviations for conflict resolution structure (N = 124)

	<i>Main Interval I</i>	<i>Main Interval II</i>	<i>t-value</i>	<i>Closing steps¹</i>
Groups accessed	8.1 (10.7)	4.9 (7.3)	3.36***	1.9 (4.5)
Polls accessed	3.5 (5.7)	2.5 (4.5)	1.79~	1.0 (2.1)
Actions implemented	13.1 (5.9)	18.5 (8.1)	10.33***	10.8 (4.9)

¹n = 79. ***p<.001. ~ p <.10.

B) Content

Gamers leaned towards a *win-win* stance (see Table 4). They took significantly more win-win actions than win-lose actions. Also, in terms of win-lose or win-win *score*, the focus was clearly on actions scoring high in the win-win category. However, I expected participants to differ in the extent to which their tendency towards win-win *outweighed* the win-lose activity. Or, to put it the other way round, in how far did the use of win-lose approximate the use of win-win actions? For later regression analyses, a difference score (win-win score minus win-lose score) was calculated expressing the degree of *win-win preponderance*. The remaining content variable action variability showed high values, ranging between .45 and 1.00, with a mean of .88 (SD = .09).

Table 4

Means and standard deviation for conflict resolution content (N = 124)

<i>Number win-lose</i>	<i>Number win-win</i>	<i>Diff.</i>	<i>t-value</i>	<i>Score win-lose</i>	<i>Score win-win</i>	<i>Diff.</i>	<i>t-value</i>
26.3 % (10.7)	62.5 % (94)	36.2% (16.9)	-26.4***	12.0 % (5.1)	51.0 % (8.4)	39.0% (12)	-36.2***

*** All t-values were significant at p <.001; a win-win stance clearly prevailed.

C) Free recall

Recall of information sources was low. In average, participants correctly recalled only 1.2 (SD=1.6) of the *poll* categories and 2.2 (SD=2.2) of the *groups* that were available.

D) Success

Similar to other investigations with PeaceMaker (Gonzalez & Martin, 2010; Gonzalez & Czlonka, in press), gamers found it hard to win the game (see Table 5). 68% lost the first game, 35% lost more than one game. Only one person was able to win. In average, participants lost 1.2 games and reached a cumulative success score of .32. Only the person winning the game reached the maximum cumulative value of 1.0. As expected, the Israeli side was clearly favored, expressed in the mean bias score of 15.9 (the Israeli approval exceeded the Palestinian approval at 15.9 points in average).

Table 5

Means and standard deviations of gaming success (N = 124)

<i>Time of first game</i>	<i>Lost games</i>	<i>Overall time</i>	<i>Bias score</i>	<i>Cumulative score</i>
1422 (660)	1.2 (1.1)	2067 (250)	15.9 (26.7)	.32 (.22)

4.1.2 Relatedness of conflict resolution strategy indicators

The different indicators of a closed strategy should be interrelated. I expected a smaller quantity of information accessed to go along with more implemented actions, more variability of actions, a smaller preponderance of win-win actions, a smaller amount of information sources recalled, more lost games, shorter gaming times (for the first game and overall), a smaller cumulative success score and a higher bias score. Table 6 shows the pattern of interrelations.¹²

¹² Index of abbreviations in Table 6 (from left to right):

Group = access of groups information; poll = polls information; actio = action frequency; n wl = number win-lose actions; n ww = number win-win actions; s ww = win-win score; s wl = win-lose score; Vary = action variability; Game overs = number of lost games; Time total = overall gaming time; Time G1= time of the first game; BIAS = approval difference score; CORE = combinatorial success score

Note, that some of the variables are per definition interrelated, like information access and recall or the win-lose and win-win indicators.

Table 6

Pattern of inter-correlations among indicators of conflict resolution strategy

	Interval I			Interval II			Closing Steps			Total game				Vary	Game overs	Time total	Time G 1	BIAS	CORE	Recall group	Recall poll
	group	poll	Actio	group	poll	actio	group	poll	actio	n wl	n ww	s wl	s ww								
1 groups	1	.60	-.19	.36	.20	-.20	.58	.22	-.11	-.19	.13	-.19	.14	-.18	-.23	.11	.23	-.08	.15	.51	.39
2 polls		1	-.08	.35	.26	-.16	.40	.23	-.13	-.11	.11	-.12	.06	-.15	-.24	.06	.18	-.15	.12	.35	.55
3 actions			1	-.09	-.02	.71	-.15	-.15	.77	.05	-.10	.07	-.13	-.19	.27	-.16	-.31	-.02	.14	.01	-.10
4 groups				1	.91	-.10	.49	.79	-.07	-.21	.21	-.20	.14	-.15	-.16	.18	.15	-.10	.14	.44	.57
5 polls					1	-.05	.38	.79	-.09	-.16	.19	-.13	.13	-.08	-.08	.13	.08	-.00	.10	.37	.55
6 actions						1	-.13	.01	.85	.06	-.09	.14	-.12	-.20	.26	.01	-.24	-.14	.20	-.01	-.11
7 groups							1	.60	-.13	-.22	.14	-.18	.10	-.11	-.17	.20	.14	-.06	.05	.39	.35
8 polls								1	-.02	-.21	.17	-.12	.11	-.19	-.11	.17	.06	-.02	.13	.39	.44
9 actions									1	.24	-.27	.24	-.26	-.11	.10	-.17	-.17	-.11	.31	-.05	-.18
14 w-los										1	-.72	.85	-.70	.48	.33	-.18	-.15	-.40	-.26	-.20	-.16
15 w-win											1	-.61	.94	-.34	-.25	.07	.10	-.18	.15	.23	.19
16 w-los												1	-.57	.46	.36	-.18	-.15	.42	-.29	-.15	-.14
17 w-win													1	-.31	-.26	.06	.06	-.16	.14	.16	.14
18 vary														1	.26	-.10	-.12	.27	-.13	-.07	-.07
19 g over															1	-.34	-.74	.48	-.68	-.08	-.13
20 tim t																1	.49	-.45	.48	.07	.13
21 tim 1																	1	-.39	.48	.15	.16
22 bias																		1	-.49	-.06	-.08
23 core																			1	.04	.10
24 recall																				1	.60
25 recall																					1

= negative correlation significant at $p < .05$
 = positive correlation significant at $p < .05$
 = marginally significant at $p < .10$

Indicators merged into a pattern of a schematic, closed-minded conflict resolution strategy. Access of groups and polls was significantly and negatively correlated with action frequency, a win-lose stance in the game, action variability and the number of lost games. Instead of searching for new information, participants took decisions based on conflict schemata (high win-lose) and turned to an uninformed actionism (high action frequency) with a random selection of actions (high action variability). The win-win and win-lose orientations were related to gaming success (number of lost games, time of the first game, the bias score and the cumulative success score) and to the additional content indicator action variability. Specifically, a stronger tendency towards win-lose went along with more lost games, a shorter duration of the first game, stronger favoritism for the Israeli side (expressed in the bias score) and a lower cumulative success score. Moreover, it was associated with lower action variability. Besides, game success was linked to action frequency: The more actions taken, the more games were lost and the shorter was the time for which a participant could keep up the first game. The overall gaming time showed only weak correlations with the other indicators of conflict resolution and was therefore not further analyzed.

4.1.3 Prediction of conflict resolution success

I calculated multiple regression analyses with SPSS to identify the indicators which predict success in the game. All predictors were forced into the model simultaneously, because theory did not suggest causal priorities. I checked for multicollinearity. Tolerance values did not fall below .46, suggesting that all predictors accounted for unique proportions of variance (see Field, 2005). The Durbin-Watson test statistic revealed that adjacent residuals were not correlated (values varied between 1.9 and 2.2; again see Field, 2005). Plots of standardized residuals against standardized predicted values suggested linear relationships between outcomes and predictors. Moreover, histograms and normal probability plots supplied support for the normal distribution assumption.

The relevant predictors for the *time of the first game* were action frequency and information use in the first 7 minutes and degree of win-win preponderance among the first actions. Two participants did not manage to play 7 minutes in their first trial. They

were excluded from the analysis. The regression analysis showed that the model explained a substantial amount of variance in the data, $F(3, 122) = 5.04, p < .01$. Results revealed *win-win preponderance* ($\beta = .25$) and *action frequency* ($\beta = -.19$) as main predictors (see Table 7). The more actions participants implemented and the less win-win orientated these actions were, the shorter did they keep up the first game. A closed, schematic style (high action frequency, high win-lose orientation) does not benefit game success.

Table 7

Summary of multiple regression analysis predicting the duration of the first game (n=122)

Predictor	Time of first game		
	b	SE b	β
Win-Win	9.13	3.25	.25**
Information	9.05	9.41	.09
Actions	-43.55	19.88	-.19*

Note. $R^2 = .11$. * $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$.

In order to predict the *number of lost games*, the *bias score* and the *cumulative success score*, I specified win-win preponderance, action frequency (in interval I and interval II), information use (interval I and interval II) and action variability as predictors. See Table 8 for the summaries. The model significantly improved the prediction of the number of lost games, $F(6, 124) = 4.78, p < .00$, the bias score, $F(6, 124) = 4.97, p < .00$, and the cumulative success score, $F(6, 124) = 3.19, p < .01$. Principal predictor for game success was win-win preponderance ($\beta = -.24, p < .01$ for the number of lost games; $\beta = -.34, p < .00$ for the bias score; $\beta = .25, p < .01$ for the cumulative success score). Those, who tended more towards a win-win stance, they lost fewer games, favored the "own" Israeli side to lesser extent (bias score), and were overall better in controlling the scenario (cumulative score).

In case of the *bias score* and *cumulative success score*, also action frequency in interval II was a strong predictor ($\beta = -.22, p < .07$ for the bias score and $\beta = .14, p < .05$ for the cumulative score). Participants who took more actions in the second half of the game were more successful and favored the Israeli side to a lesser extent. However, it is likely

that those who were more successful simply felt confident enough at the end of the game to implement many actions.

Table 8

Summary of multiple regression analysis predicting the number of lost games, the bias score and the cumulative success score (N = 124)

Predictor	Number games lost			Bias score			Cumulative score		
	b	SE b	β	b	SE b	β	b	SE b	β
Win-Win	-.02	.01	-.24**	-1.10	.30	-.34***	.01	.00	.25**
Information I	-.01	.02	.09	-.18	.33	-.05	.00	.00	.14
Information II	-.01	.01	-.04	-.22	.49	-.04	.00	.00	.07
Actions I	.03	.02	.13	.25	.78	.04	.00	.00	.02
Actions II	.01	.02	.09	-1.07	.58	-.22~	.01	.00	.14*
Variability	1.32	1.15	.11	61.82	38.62	.15	-.03	.23	-.01

Note. For number of games lost: $R^2 = .20$. For the bias score: $R^2 = .21$. For the cumulative success score: $R^2 = .14$. ** $p < .01$. * $p < .05$. *** $p < .000$.

In sum, the results of the multiple regression analyses reflected the functional principle of the scenario. Those who chose actions that benefitted both sides (win-win actions) were able to reconcile the opposing interests and came closer to a resolution of the conflict.

4.2 IDENTITY VARIABLES AND CONTROL VARIABLES

How were the identity variables distributed in this sample? How did they relate to the control variables?

4.2.1 Identity variables

Table 9 shows the distribution of participants over the three categorical identity variables religion, geo-cultural origin and affiliation. Not surprisingly, most Christians came from Western Europe. They were equally affiliated to the Palestinian ($n = 22$) and Israeli side ($n = 23$). Muslims, a majority with geo-cultural origin in Western Asia, were Palestine-affiliated. Participants with Jewish religion featured various regions of origin

and indicated affiliation with the Israeli side. For the inter-correlations of the categorical identity variables see Appendix D1.

Table 9

Distribution of participants in terms of geo-cultural origin, religion and affiliation

	Western Europe				Eastern Europe				Israel-Palestine (IP)				Western Asia without IP					USA				
	C	M	J	N	C	M	J	N	C	M	J	N	C	M	J	N	O ²	C	M	J	N	
<i>Religion¹</i>																						
<i>Affiliation</i>																						
Palestine	22	1	-	7	-	-	-	1	1	3	-	-	1	10	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	
Israel	23	-	3	3	-	-	7	3	-	-	4	-	-	-	-	1		1	-	2	-	
None	18	1	-	7	1	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	-	

¹ C = Christian, M = Muslim, J = Jewish, N = no religion

² O = other religion (in the other categories of origin, "other religion" was not represented and thus not specified in the Table).

The continuous identity variable value-based involvement (M = 3.12; SD = .71) correlated moderately with religion ($r = .38, p < .01$), geo-cultural origin ($r = .40, p < .01$) and affiliation with Palestine ($r = .18, p < .05$).

4.2.2 Control variables

See Appendix E1 for the descriptive data and results of one-way between groups ANOVAs. As expected, *knowledge* was an important control variable. Those who were identity-associated knew more about the conflict. A multiple regression with religion, geo-cultural origin¹³, value-based involvement and affiliation with Israel as well as Palestine as independent variables revealed value-involvement, $\beta = .53$, and affiliation with the Israeli side, $\beta = .21, p < .05$, as main predictors of knowledge about the conflict. In one-way ANOVAs, this was reflected in significant between-groups differences for affiliation, $F(2, 124) = 3.1, p < .05$. Post-hoc Bonferroni tests showed that both Israeli and Palestine-affiliated knew more about the conflict than non-affiliated participants.

¹³ For regression analyses, religion and cultural origin were dummy coded. For *religion*: 1 = highly conflict relevant religion (Jewish and Muslim); 2 = lowly conflict relevant (Christian, no and other religion). For *geo-cultural origin*: 1 = region affected by the conflict (Western Asia); 2 = region not affected (other).

It was further examined if the identity variables would impact feelings of control, as manifest in *fear of failure* and *feelings of dominance*. Because identity associated persons knew more about the conflict, which in turn might have led to more feelings of control, I included knowledge about the conflict as control variable. A simultaneous multiple regression revealed *religion* as main predictor for *fear of failure*, $\beta = -.24$, $p < .05$. Jewish and Muslim participants were substantially less afraid of being unsuccessful in the scenario. Knowledge was the second significant predictor, $\beta = -.24$, $p < .05$. Those who knew more about the conflict were less anxious to fail.

In order to assess the development of *dominance*, I calculated a latent growth curve model (LGM) in a structural equation modeling (SEM, Bollen, 1989) approach. MPlus 5.0 was used for the SEM calculations (Muthén & Muthén, 2007). In LGM, two factors describe developments (see Figure 9). The *level factor* describes the initial level (level mean) and individual differences in the initial level (level variance). It is constant across time and factor loadings are set 1 for each point in time. In the *slope factor*, the rate of change is expressed (slope mean) and individual differences in the rate of change (slope variance).

I assumed *dominance* to show a linear development. Participants should feel continuously less in control, owing to the difficulty of the scenario. Thus, factor loadings were fixed to model linear change ($t_0 = 0$, $t_1 = 1$, $t_2 = 2$; see Figure 9). Results revealed that the growth trajectories were linear, as anticipated. *Dominance* decreased in the course of the game (Figure 8). For the initial mean, mplus estimated $\beta = 4.71$, $p < .00$, the estimated rate of change resulted highly negative, $\beta = -.32$, $p < .00$. There was significant variability on the initial level, $\beta = .74$, $p < .000$, suggesting meaningful inter-individual differences. Variance of the slope (rate of change) was smaller, $\beta = .20$, $p < .10$ (see the summary in Figure 9). The linear LGM showed good fit¹⁴: $\chi^2 (1) = 0.531$, $p = .466$, $CFI = 1.00$, $TLI = 1.016$, $RMSEA = .00$ (Confidence Interval 90%, $CI = .00, .21$), $SRMR = 0.014$.

¹⁴ Note. Fit refers to the model's ability to reproduce the variance-covariance matrix. The χ^2 value is supposed to be non-significant. The Comparative Fit Index (CFI) and Tucker Lewis Index (TLI) should be above .90. Good models have a Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) of .05 or less and a Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) of .08 or less. The Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) and sample-size adjusted Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) are used for model comparison and indicate a better fit when smaller (Bollen & Curran, 2006).

Figure 8. The development of dominance during the game over three measuring times.

Figure 9. The linear latent growth curve model for dominance with estimators of means and variances. Coefficients are unstandardized estimators. *** $p < .001$.

Subsequently, I defined the identity variables and knowledge as predictors of the dominance initial level and rate of change. Results revealed only *value-involvement* as significant predictor of the dominance initial level, $\beta = .35$, $p < .001$ ($R^2 = .12$). More value-involvement went along with substantially more feelings of dominance right before gaming. None of the identity variables predicted the rate of change. The model with value-involvement as predictor showed excellent data fit: $\chi^2(4) = 3.35$, $p = .50$, $CFI = 1.00$, $TLI = 1.01$, $RMSEA = .00$ (Confidence Interval 90%, $CI = .00, .13$), $SRMR = 0.04$.

Finally, identity was neither relevant for the final school grade ($M = 1.72$; $SD = .68$), nor for average gaming hours per week ($M = 1.33$; $SD = 3.71$). They were not part of

further analyses. English proficiency was quite evenly distributed, only participants from the USA were considerably more skilled than the others. Control variables were checked for correlations with the conflict resolution indicators (see Appendix D2). *Fear of failure* correlated significantly with action frequency in interval I, the *dominance initial level* with action variability.¹⁵

To recap, identity association was associated with more conflict-specific knowledge, as well as less fear of failure and more feelings of dominance right before gaming.

4.3 HYPOTHESIS 1: IDENTITY VARIABLES AND CONFLICT RESOLUTION

Does identity association predict closed-minded conflict resolution behavior? I will first describe the group differences between (1) Palestine-, Israel-, and non-affiliated participants, (2) Christian, Muslim, Jewish and non-religious groups and (3) participants of different geo-cultural backgrounds (4.3.1). Then, results of hierarchical multiple regression analyses with identity variables as predictors are presented (4.3.2).

4.3.1 *Group differences in conflict resolution behavior*

Group differences suggested that identity association was related to a more closed-minded conflict resolution style. Appendices E2-E4 show all group means and standard deviations and results of one-way ANOVAs. The closed processing mode was most strongly expressed in the use of less information sources and worse subsequent recall. Participants who were Israel- or Palestine- affiliated, Muslim or Jewish, and/or originating from Western Asia, accessed significantly less information sources and (accordingly) recalled a smaller amount of information than non-affiliated, non-religious, or Western European participants. Also in line with a more closed-minded style, participants from Israel-Palestine implemented substantially more actions than

¹⁵ Note that fear of failure and dominance had been assessed in order to avoid confounds with identity-induced affect effects. However, since identity did neither predict action frequency nor variability, as shown in 4.3, these variables are not further analysed.

participants from Western Europe in the first 14 minutes of gaming. A closed processing mode was moreover expressed in lower win-win preponderance. Participants affiliated to both Israel and Palestine assumed a stance marked by less win-win and more win-lose focus than non-affiliated participants.

The group originating from Israel-Palestine had the lowest win-win preponderance. Nonetheless, they reached the highest cumulative success score. As has been shown in 4.1.3, low win-win preponderance was associated with low game success. Where, then, does this contradiction come from? Persons originating from Israel-Palestine had the highest conflict-specific knowledge. Knowledge seemed to predict gaming success beyond the effect of win-win preponderance (see the following paragraph).

As far as religion was concerned, participants with Jewish religion were best in controlling the scenario, although group differences resulted non significant. This contrasted with preliminary research on the PeaceMaker scenario by Coty Gonzalez et al. They demonstrated that participants reporting Judaism as religious affiliation were less successful than persons of other religions (Gonzalez, Czonka, & Eisenberg, under review). No significant group differences appeared between (a) Jewish and Muslim persons or (b) participants from global Western Asia and the Israel-Palestinian territories. It was only decisive whether participants' religion or geo-cultural background were immediately associated with the conflict in Israel-Palestine or not.

So, identity association was associated with a closed conflict resolution mode. In further analyses, I aimed to examine which identity variables most powerfully predicted the processing strategy.

4.3.2 Conflict resolution strategy predicted by identity

Hierarchical multiple regression analyses were carried out in order to test for the effects of control and identity variables on conflict resolution strategy. Dependent

variables were *information use* (interval I and II),¹⁶ *action frequency* (interval I and II), *information recall*, *win-win preponderance* (win-win score minus win-lose score), *action variability*, *bias score* and the *cumulative success score* in which the other indicators of gaming success were combined (see 2.2.2).

Independent variables were entered in three blocks according to assumed causal priorities, as recommended by Cohen, Cohen, West and Aiken (2003, p. 158). Religion (high vs. low conflict relevant) and geo-cultural origin (region affected vs. non-affected by the conflict) were expected to underlie differences in knowledge, feelings of control, value-based involvement and affiliation. They were entered first. The second block comprised the control variables knowledge and English proficiency. Third, value-involvement, affiliation to Israel, and affiliation to Palestine were included in the equation. In each block, all predictors were forced into the model simultaneously. The identity variables were correlated (see Appendix D1). Therefore, I carefully checked for multicollinearity. None of the independent variables in the regression equations had a tolerance smaller than .45, suggesting that all accounted for unique proportions of variance (Field, 2005). Values of the Durbin-Watson test statistic ranged between 1.8 and 2.4, indicating independence of residuals (Ibid). Plots of standardized residuals against standardized predicted values indicated linear relationships between outcomes and predictors. However, there were signs for heteroscedasticity of residuals for the predicted variables *information I and II*, suggesting some caution for generalization of the model to the population. Histograms and normal probability plots for the residuals did not show any substantial deviations from normal distributions.

A) Structure

For *frequency of information use in interval I*, step 1 significantly improved the prediction of the outcome variable, $F(2, 124) = 6.11, p < .005$. For *information use in interval II*, the improvement was marginally significant, $F(2, 121) = 2.90, p < .06$. Results

¹⁶ Note that information use only refers to the access of the *groups* information category since *polls* showed little variance (see 4.1.2). However, descriptive statistics indicated the same relationships with identity variables for *polls* as for *groups*.

revealed a significant main effect for religion ($\beta_{\text{religion}} = -.22$ for *information I* and $\beta_{\text{religion}} = -.24$ for *information II*, $p < .05$). Muslim and Jewish participants used considerably fewer information sources. In the case of *action frequency*, step 2 significantly improved the prediction, $F(4, 124) = 5.22$, $p < .001$ for *action I*, and $F(4, 121) = 4.71$, $p < .001$ for *action II*. Action frequency was significantly predicted by knowledge about the conflict and English proficiency ($\beta_{\text{knowledge}} = .23$ for *action I* and $.29$ for *action II*, $\beta_{\text{English}} = .28$ for *action I* and $.19$ for *action II*, $p < .05$). Those who knew more about the conflict and those who were better in English implemented more actions. See a summary in Table 10.

Table 10

Hierarchical multiple regression analyses predicting structure (information use and action frequency) in intervals I (N = 124) and II (n = 121)

Predictor	Info use I			Info use II			Action I			Action II		
	b	SE b	β	b	SE b	β	b	SE b	β	b	SE b	β
Step 1												
Religion	-5.33	2.59	-.22*	-3.99	1.79	-.24*	-.35	1.5	-.03	-.65	2.02	-.04
Origin	-3.51	2.94	-.13	.97	2.03	.05	1.89	1.69	.12	3.12	2.29	.15
Step 2												
Religion	-5.65	2.67	-.23*	-3.69	1.84	-.22*	-.68	1.43	-.05	-1.49	1.95	-.08
Origin	-3.53	2.96	-.13	.98	2.03	.05	2.00	1.58	.13	3.21	2.16	.15
Knowldg	.16	.33	.05	-.20	.23	-.08	.46	.18	.23**	.79	.24	.29**
English	-.13	.73	-.02	-.03	.50	-.01	1.30	.40	.28**	1.14	.53	.19*
Step 3												
Religion	-5.65	2.83	-.23*	-3.83	1.95	-.23*	-1.21	1.56	-.09	-1.76	2.11	-.10
Origin	-5.25	3.20	-.19	2.04	2.21	.11	2.41	1.73	.16	2.02	2.35	.10
Knowldg	-.08	.38	-.02	-.18	.26	-.07	.39	.21	.19~	.55	.28	.20*
English	-.29	.74	-.04	-.05	.51	-.01	1.15	.40	.26**	.95	.54	.16~
Values	2.66	1.70	.18	-.17	1.18	-.02	.05	.92	.01	2.30	1.24	.20~
Israel	-1.82	2.63	-.08	-.50	1.83	-.03	-.33	1.42	-.03	-1.67	1.94	-.10
Palestine	-.91	2.57	-.04	-2.71	1.77	-.18	-.75	1.40	-.06	-1.31	1.89	-.08

Note. Information I: $R^2 = .09$ for step 1 ($ps < .005$). $\Delta R^2 = .00$ for step 2. $\Delta R^2 = .02$ for step 3. Information II: $R^2 = .05$ for step 1 ($ps < .06$). $\Delta R^2 = .01$ for step 2. $\Delta R^2 = .03$ for step 3. Action I: $R^2 = .01$ for step 1. $\Delta R^2 = .14$ for step 2 ($ps < .000$). $\Delta R^2 = .02$ for step 3. Action II: $R^2 = .02$ for step 1. $\Delta R^2 = .12$ for step 2 ($ps < .000$). $\Delta R^2 = .03$ for step 3. ~ $p < .10$. * $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$.

B) Free recall

In order to validly predict information recall, I controlled for the average number of information accessed per minute. Recall was best predicted by step 3, $F(7, 124) = 8.69$, $p < .000$. Results revealed affiliation with Israel and Palestine as crucial identity variable. Those with affiliation to one of the conflict parties showed significantly worse recall of information encountered in the conflict scenario. The effect was considerably stronger for Israeli affiliation, $\beta = -.25$, than for Palestinian affiliation, $\beta = -.18$. See column 1 in Table 11.

C) Content

The difference between win-win and win-lose scores (*win-win preponderance*) expressed whether persons adopted a clear win-win stance or not. The more participants tended towards *win-lose*, the smaller the discrepancy between win-win and win-lose scores became (low win-win preponderance). In order to account for the pure *score* difference, I included the difference between the *number* of win-win and win-lose actions as further control variable in the equation. Step 3 explained the most variance in *win-win preponderance* and significantly improved its prediction, $F(8, 124) = 153.64$, $p < .000$. Value-involvement was the principal predictor with $\beta = -.12$, $p < .005$. Those whose values were related to the conflict leaned more towards a win-lose stance. Also, the prediction of *action variability* was clearly improved by step 3, $F(9, 124) = 1.86$, $p < .07$. English proficiency was the main predictor ($\beta_{\text{English}} = .23$, $p < .05$). Those with better English knowledge implemented a more varying range of actions. See column 2 and 3 in Table 11 for all regression parameters.

D) Success

Step 2 significantly improved the prediction of the *bias score*, $F(4, 124) = 3.60$, $p < .01$. Results revealed *knowledge* as main predictor, $\beta = -.27$, $p < .005$. The more knowledge about the conflict a participant had, the less was the Israeli side favored. The prediction of the *cumulative success score* was significantly enhanced by step 2 as well, $F(4, 124) = 2.57$, $p < .05$. *English proficiency* and *knowledge* appeared as principal predictors, $\beta_{\text{English}} = .17$ and $\beta_{\text{Knowledge}} = .18$, $p < .05$. The more someone knew about the

topic and the better someone was in English, the more successful was the conflict resolution task. See Table 12 (p. 58) for all estimators.

Table 11

Hierarchical multiple regression analysis predicting information recall, win-win preponderance and action variability (N = 124)

Predictor	Information recall			Win-win preponderance			Variability		
	b	SE b	β	b	SE b	β	b	SEb	β
Step 1									
Religion	-.95	.46	-.19*	-.18	.99	-.01	-.04	.02	-.19~
Origin	.29	.50	.05	.91	1.13	.03	.04	.03	.15
(Number) ¹				.68	.02	.95***			
(Info use) ²	2.0	.31	.52***						
Step 2									
Religion	-.91	.47	-.19*	.43	.97	.02	-.03	.02	-.16
Origin	.30	.51	.06	.89	1.09	.03	.04	.03	.16
Knowledge	-.01	.06	-.01	-.40	.12	-.10**	.00	.00	-.01
English	.07	.13	.05	-.11	.26	-.01	.01	.01	.19*
(Number)				.67	.02	.95***			
(Info use)	2.01	.31	.52***						
Step 3									
Religion	-.56	.49	-.11	1.31	1.0	.05	-.04	.03	-.18
Origin	.30	.54	.05	1.45	1.13	.05	.06	.03	.23~
Knowledge	.05	-.06	.06	-.17	.13	-.04	.00	.00	.01
English	.06	.12	.04	-.02	.26	-.00	.02	.01	.23*
Values	-.25	.29	-.08	-1.92	.60	-.12**	.01	.02	.04
Israel	-1.10	.44	-.25*	-1.32	.92	-.05	.03	.02	.17
Palestine	-.78	.44	-.18~	-.66	.90	-.03	.00	.02	.02
(Number)				.66	.02	.93***			
(Info use)	2.00	.31	.52***						

Note. Win-win preponderance: $R^2 = .89$ for step 1 ($ps < .00$). $\Delta R^2 = .01$ for step 2 ($ps < .005$). $\Delta R^2 = .01$ for step 3 ($ps < .05$).

Variability: $R^2 = .03$ for step 1. $\Delta R^2 = .03$ for step 2. $\Delta R^2 = .07$ for step 3 ($ps < .05$).

Recall: $R^2 = .34$ for step 1 ($ps < .00$). $\Delta R^2 = .00$ for step 2. $\Delta R^2 = .04$ for step 3 ($ps < .10$).

* $p < .05$. ** $p < .005$. *** $p < .001$.

¹ The difference between the number of win-win and win-lose actions. A control variable only included for the prediction of win-win preponderance.

² Average of use of information sources in the game. A control variable only for information recall.

In sum, regression analyses confirmed that identity association leads to a closed-minded conflict resolution style. Moreover, results revealed differential effects of identity variables. Conflict solvers with a highly conflict associated *religion* (Jewish or Muslim) focused substantially less on the external information provided, as expressed in a low frequency of information access. Persons who indicated *affiliation* with either the Palestinian or Israeli side were worse in recalling the information given in the scenario. *Value-based involvement* predicted a stronger tendency towards a win-lose stance in the conflict. The more value-based the participants were, the more did they act like a stereotypic, hawkish Israeli Prime-Minister and implemented actions that primarily benefited the Israeli side. Notably, this effect of value-based involvement was independent from affiliation with Israel or Palestine. Last but not least, results highlighted the importance of *knowledge* for problem solving. Those with more knowledge about the conflict implemented more actions and were better in controlling the scenario; i.e., they were able to comply with the interests of both sides.

Effects of affiliation with a conflict party

In contrast to findings by Gonzalez and Martin (2010), the bias score was not predicted by affiliation. Looking at the group means (Appendix E3), both the Palestine- and Israel-affiliated participants favored the “own” Israeli side to a lesser extent than non-affiliated participants (Bias non-affiliated group: $M = 18.5$, $SD = 29.2$, Israel-affiliated: $M = 15.5$, $SD = 25.5$, Palestine-affiliated: $M = 14.6$, $SD = 26.8$). The greater knowledge of the Israel- and Palestine- affiliated persons apparently resulted into the smaller bias. In fact, it did not make any difference whether persons were affiliated with Israel or Palestine. This was also expressed in identification with the role of the Israeli Prime minister. Both groups identified themselves more strongly with the role than non-affiliated participants (Israel- affiliated: $M = 4.80$, $SD = 1.75$; Palestine-affiliated: $M = 4.30$, $SD = 1.82$; Non-affiliated: $M = 3.23$, $SD = 1.48$), as revealed by a one-way ANOVA, $F(2, 124) = 7.69$, $p < .001$.

Table 12

Hierarchical multiple regression analysis predicting the gaming success indicators bias and cumulative score (N = 124)

<i>Predictor</i>	Bias			Cumulative score		
	b	SE b	β	b	SEb	β
Step 1						
Religion	-6.61	6.69	-.11	-.00	.06	-.00
Origin	1.10	7.58	.02	.07	.06	.13
Step 2						
Religion	-3.80	6.56	-.06	-.01	.06	-.03
Origin	.91	7.26	.01	.08	.06	.13
Knowledge	-2.42	.80	-.27**	.01	.00	.18*
English	-3.10	1.78	-.15~	.03	.02	.17*
Step 3						
Religion	-3.76	7.01	-.06	-.01	.06	-.02
Origin	2.67	7.96	.04	.07	.07	.12
Knowledge	-2.22	.94	-.25*	.01	.01	.17
English	-3.01	1.82	-.15~	.03	.02	.20*
Values	-1.94	4.22	-.05	.02	.04	.07
Israel	.59	6.50	.01	.03	.06	.07
Palestine	-1.21	6.34	-.02	.02	.05	.04

Note. Bias: $R^2 = .01$ for step 1. $\Delta R^2 = .10$ for step 2 ($ps < .005$). $\Delta R^2 = .003$ for step 3.

Success: $R^2 = .02$ for step 1. $\Delta R^2 = .06$ for step 2 ($ps < .05$). $\Delta R^2 = .003$ for step 3.

** $p < .005$. * $p < .05$.

4.4 HYPOTHESIS 2: MEDIATION BY AFFECT

I will now address the question whether the observed relationships between religion and use of information (4.4.2), affiliation and information recall (4.4.3) and value-based involvement and win-win preponderance (4.4.4) were mediated by affect. Before that, results for affect in the whole sample are reported.

4.4.1 Affect in the whole sample

A) Valence

Latent growth curve. The change in affective valence was assessed with a latent growth curve model (LGM) approach (Mplus 5, Muthén & Muthén, 2007). A linear pattern of development was assumed for affective valence. Participants were expected to shift from a challenge appraisal (positive valence, values above 4) to a threat appraisal (negative valence, values below 4). Thus, factor loadings were fixed to model linear change ($t_0=0$, $t_1 = 1$, $t_2 =2$, see Figure 11). Results revealed that the growth trajectories were linear, as anticipated. Valence decreased in the course of the game. Participants tended to have positive feelings before starting the game ($M = 4.8$) and after twenty minutes of gaming, the average valence was slightly negative ($M=3.8$). Accordingly, the mean rate of change was negative, $\beta = -.52$, $p < .001$ (see Figure 10). Figure 11 shows means and variances for the initial level and rate of change. Significant inter-individual variability was given for the initial mean (intercept), $\beta = .67$, $p < .001$, as well as for the estimated slope, $\beta =.29$, $p < .05$. The significant variance suggested a possible impact of covariates like religion, affiliation or value-involvement. The linear latent growth curve model showed good fit: $\chi^2(3) = 3.624$, $p = .305$, $CFI = .98$, $TLI = .98$, $RMSEA = .04$ (Confidence Interval 90%, $CI = .00, .16$), $SRMR = .07$.

Figure 10. Development of affective valence ($n = 124$).

Figure 11. The linear latent growth curve model for affective valence. Coefficients are unstandardized estimators. *** $p < .001$. ** $p < .01$.

B) Arousal

On the whole, the arousal values of the three measuring points showed a high degree of similarity: $t_0 = 4.01$ (1.2), $t_1 = 4.53$ (1.2), $t_2 = 4.22$ (1.2); Cronbach's $\alpha = .73$. The linear latent growth curve model did not fit the data. The introduction of a quadratic slope to the equation produced a psi matrix error, indicating overfactoring. A piecewise model showed poor fit (see Bollen & Curran, 2006; Duncan, 2004). Therefore, I used the overall arousal mean in further analyses, averaged over the three measured points.

4.4.2 Religion, affect and the use of information sources

According to Baron and Kenny (1986), the relationship between religion and information use is completely mediated by affect, if (a) religion is significantly related to information use as well as (b) to the hypothesized mediator affect, and if (c) affect predicts information use when religion is in the equation with (d) a reduction of religion effects to non-significance. In 4.3.2, religion was shown to predict the frequency of information use in interval I and interval II, satisfying condition (a).

A) Valence

The *initial level* and *rate of change* of the latent growth curve of valence was regressed on religion (dummy coded with 1 for high conflict-associated and 0 for low

conflict-associated). Religion predicted the initial level with marginal significance, $\beta = .23$, $p < .10$, and significantly predicted the rate of change, $\beta = -.36$, $p < .05$. Persons with a highly conflict-associated religion had indicated a higher (i.e. more positive) initial level of valence ($\beta = 5.00$) and they experienced a stronger drop in pleasure (smaller rate of change; $\beta = -.79$) than participants with a lowly conflict-associated religion (Initial level: $\beta = 4.62$, rate of change: $\beta = -.42$). See the summary in Table 13. Thus, Muslim and Jewish participants felt more positive at the beginning than non-religious or Christian participants and after 10 minutes, they already felt worse (see Figure 12 for the latent growth curves of the two groups). Intercept and slope were negatively correlated, $\beta = -.42$, $p < .05$; the more positive the valence at the beginning, the smaller (more negative) the slope. The linear LGC with religion-based conflict association as covariate fit the data well: $\chi^2(4) = 4.00$, $p = .41$, $CFI = 1.00$, $TLI = 1.00$, $RMSEA = .00$ (Confidence Interval 90%, $CI = .00, .14$), $SRMR = 0.06$. Thus mediation condition (b) was satisfied for affective valence.

Table 14 provides further details. In the first 10 minutes, the affective valence of Jewish participants dropped less (-.88) than the valence of Muslim participants (-1.10). However, in the subsequent minutes (between minutes 10 to 20), they turned to feel considerably worse than the gamers with Muslim orientation (reduction of pleasure by -.86 as compared to -.06).

Figure 12. The linear latent growth curve models for high and low conflict-relevant religion. Coefficients are unstandardized estimators. *** $p < .001$. ** $p < .01$.

Table 13

Latent Growth Curve Model parameters of the two religion groups (N = 124)

Valence Latent Growth Curve Model							
Group 1: High conflict association				Group 2: Low conflict association			
Initial level		Rate of change		Initial level		Rate of change	
<i>Mean</i>	<i>Variance</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Variance</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Variance</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Variance</i>
5.0***	.15	-.79***	.13	4.62***	.92***	-.42	.31*

Note. Group 1: n = 31. Group 2: n = 93. Coefficients are unstandardized estimators. *** p<.001. **p < .01. *p < .05. ~p<.10.

Table 14

Group differences in valence measuring points (N = 124)

	<i>Christian</i> (N=67)	<i>Muslim</i> (N=15)	<i>Jewish</i> (N=16)	<i>No religion</i> (N=24)	<i>Other</i> (N=2)
Valence to	4.71 (1.33)	5.03 (1.03)	5.07 (1.31)	4.63 (1.21)	5.50 (.71)
Valence t ₁	4.20 (1.20)	3.93 (1.49)	4.19 (1.28)	4.13 (1.19)	4.00 (.00)
Valence t ₂	3.93 (1.28)	3.87 (1.73)	3.33 (1.54)	4.00 (1.08)	4.00 (1.41)
Average	4.28 (.96)	4.28 (1.01)	4.20 (.91)	4.25 (.87)	4.50(.24)

In order to satisfy conditions (c) and (d), the valence LGM should predict information use in interval I and II when religion is in the equation, with a reduction of the relationship between religion and information use to non-significance. See Figure 13 for the model and the results. The path between religion and *information use I* remained significant ($\beta = -.32, p < .01$). *Information use I* was not predicted by the valence rate of change. Jewish and Muslim participants accessed substantially less information in period I of gaming *not* as a result of emotional valence. Things were different for *information use II*. With inclusion of the valence latent growth curve in the equation, *information use II* ceased to be predicted by religion. Instead, the path between *valence rate of change* and *information use II* was significant $\beta = .41, p < .05$. Those with a smaller valence rate of change, experiencing a stronger drop in affective valence, accessed less information sources in interval II. Congruent with earlier analyses, *religion* was a significant predictor

of the valence rate of change ($\beta = -.36, p < .05$); the pleasantness ratings of those with a conflict-associated religion decreased more.

Figure 13. Results of model 1; information use predicted by religion and the latent growth curve of affective valence. R^2 (initial valence) = .05. R^2 (valence slope) = .13. R^2 (info use I) = .09. R^2 (info use II) = .19. $n = 121$.

Thus, the effect from religion on *information use II* shown in 4.3.2 was fully mediated by the development of affective valence. Muslim and Jewish participants experienced a stronger decrease of pleasure and therefore used less information sources in the second part of the game. As shown in Table 15 (label: model 1), model fit proved excellent.

In order to comply with the principle of model parsimony, I defined a model (model 2) with a direct path between religion and information use in interval I, and an indirect relationship between religion and information use II being fully mediated by the rate of affective valence (see Figure 14). Again, these direct and indirect paths were highly significant ($p < .01$). Fit indices revealed that the model explained the data very well (Table 15).

Figure 14. Results of model 2; information use predicted by religion with information use II fully mediated by the valence rate of change. R^2 (initial valence) = .05. R^2 (valence slope) = .15. R^2 (info use I) = .08. R^2 (info use II) = .23. All estimators are STDYX standardized. *** $p < .001$. ** $p < .01$. * $p < .05$. $\sim p < .10$. $n = 121$.

I compared the fit of this parsimonious model 2 with the larger mediation model 1 in order to find out if the larger model with more degrees of freedom fits the data significantly better than the smaller model. See Table 15. The χ^2 difference test was non-significant, showing that the parsimonious model 2 did not fit the data worse than the larger model 1 (χ^2 diff (3) = 0.20, ns). Also, the AIC and sample-size adjusted BIC of the parsimonious model were smaller, indicating better fit.

Table 15

Comparison of fit between the two models

Model	χ^2	CFI	TLI	AIC	Adj BIC	SRMR	RMSEA	χ^2 diff
Model 1	7.79 (7), $p = .35$.99	.97	3040	3034	.06	.03	-
Model 2	7.99 (10), $p = .63$	1.00	1.05	3034	3029	.05	.00	
Difference model 1 and 2	-	-	-	-6	-5	-	-	.20 (3)

CFI = Comparative fit index, TLI = Tucker Lewis Index, AIC = Akaike Information Criterion, adj BIC = sample-size adjusted Bayesian Information Criterion, SRMR = Standardized Root Mean Square Residual, RMSEA = Root Mean Square Error of Approximation.

To recap, religion influenced participants' information access behavior and affective valence. The influence of religion on information use in a later phase of gaming (starting from minute 14) was mediated by the development of valence. Those with a highly conflict-associated religion, whose affective valence turned considerably more negative during the game, employed less information sources. In order to test whether in fact the valence rate of change and not the individual measurements of valence were predictive for information use II, I identified the three measured points as predictors. The only significant relationship consisted between information II and valence in minute 20, $\beta = .25$, $p < .05$. However, regression of information use II on the valence latent growth curve *and* valence 20 simultaneously revealed that the single measuring point had no explanatory power beyond the valence slope. The way in which the affective valence changed was crucial, not how participants felt in separate moments of the game.

B) Arousal

A second possible mediator of the relationship between religion and use of information sources was the arousal dimension of affect. Religion (highly vs. lowly conflict-associated) significantly predicted arousal, $\beta = .25$, $p < .01$.¹⁷ Those with a highly conflict-associated religion indicated higher arousal levels. Table 16 shows the differences between the religion groups. Group differences in religion were marginally significant for average arousal, $F(4, 124) = 2.1$, and arousal at t_1 , $F(4, 124) = 2.1$. A post-hoc Bonferroni test showed that the distinction was most pronounced between Muslim orientation on the one hand and Christian orientation or no religious preference on the other hand ($p < .05$ for average arousal, $p < .06$ for arousal at t_1 , $p < .05$ for arousal at t_2). The arousal of persons of Jewish religion was also higher than that of Christian or non-religious participants at t_1 as well as in average, but the difference did not go beyond marginal significance, with p-values between .07 and .13.

¹⁷ $b = .57$, $SE\ b = .20$, $R^2 = .06$

However, arousal did *not* predict information use. Hence, mediation of the relationship between religion and information use was only by the valence dimension of affect.

Table 16

Group differences in arousal for the religion groups (n = 124)

	<i>Christian</i>	<i>Muslim</i>	<i>Jewish</i>	<i>No religion</i>	<i>Other religion</i>
Arousal t ₀	3.9 (1.2)	4.4 (1.7)	4.4 (1.1)	3.9 (.90)	4.0 (.00)
Arousal t ₁	4.4 (1.1)	5.0 (1.1)	4.9 (1.3)	4.2 (1.1)	3.5 (.70)
Arousal t ₂	4.1 (1.2)	4.9 (1.5)	4.3 (1.4)	4.0 (1.1)	4.0 (.00)
Average	4.1 (.96)	4.8 (1.1)	4.5 (1.1)	4.0 (.87)	3.8 (.24)

4.4.3 Affiliation, arousal and information recall

Conform to results concerning *religion* presented above, also the broader variable of *affiliation with Israel and Palestine* was a main predictor for the arousal dimension of affect. This was shown by hierarchical multiple regression analyses with all identity variables specified as independent variables (see a summary in Table 18). Step 3 best explained the variance in arousal, $F(7, 124) = 2.91, p < .005$. Israel-affiliation, $\beta = .34$, as well as Palestine-affiliation, $\beta = .37$, predicted arousal at $p < .005$. Thus, participants who had indicated an affiliation with a conflict party felt substantially more aroused. Table 17 shows the group means for Israel-, Palestine- and non-affiliated persons. Persons with affiliation to Israel or Palestine were not distinctively aroused. However, these two groups differed significantly from the non-affiliated group ($p < .001$ for t₀ and the average arousal, $p < .02$ for t₁, $p < .01$ for t₂; $F_{t_0}(2, 124) = 7.0, p < .001$, $F_{t_1}(2) = 4.6, p < .05$, $F_{t_2}(2, 124) = 4.5, p < .05$). The group differences were most visible in the average arousal with $F(2, 124) = 9.3, p = .000$.

In order to test the mediation according to Baron and Kenny (1986), further hierarchical multiple regression analyses were calculated (see the second column in Table 18). In step 1, affiliation with Israel and Palestine, as well as frequency of information use as control variable were specified in the equation; in step 2, arousal was entered. Arousal strongly predicted information recall ($\beta = -.46, p = .000$). The relationship between

affiliation and recall became non-significant once arousal was included. The effect of identity association on recall was thus completely mediated by arousal.

Table 17

Group differences in arousal for the non-affiliated, Israeli-affiliated and Palestine-affiliated group (N = 124)

	<i>Non- affiliated (N = 30)</i>	<i>Israel- affiliated (N = 47)</i>	<i>Palestine-affiliated (N = 47)</i>	<i>Total sample (N = 124)</i>
Arousal t0	3.33 (.84)	4.26 (1.10)	4.21 (1.35)	4.02 (1.21)
Arousal t1	3.93 (.96)	4.57 (1.24)	4.72 (1.12)	4.48 (1.17)
Arousal t2	3.54 (.93)	4.40 (1.31)	4.36 (1.25)	4.19 (1.25)
Average	3.57 (.69)	4.39 (.97)	4.42 (1.02)	4.20 (.99)

Table 18

Hierarchical regression to predict arousal and information recall (N = 124)

		Arousal			Information recall			
<i>Predictor</i>	b	SE b	B	<i>Predictor</i>	b	SE b	β	
Step 1				Step 1				
Religion	.58	.24	.26*	Israel	-1.22	.41	-.28**	
Origin	-.03	.28	-.01	Palestine	-.90	.41	-.20*	
Step 2				Step 2				
Religion	.52	.25	.23*	Info use	2.06	.29	.53***	
Origin	-.04	.28	-.02	Israel	-.42	.37	-.10	
Knowledge	.02	.03	.05	Palestine	-.09	.37	-.02	
English	-.10	.07	-.13	Info use	1.99	.25	.51***	
Step 3				Step 3				
Religion	.36	.25	.16	Arousal	-.99	.15	-.46***	
Origin	-.08	.29	-.03					
Knowledge	.00	.03	.00					
English	-.08	.07	-.11					
Values	.02	.15	.02					
Israel	.69	.24	.34**					
Palestine	.75	.23	.37**					

Note. Arousal: $R^2 = .06$ for step 1 ($ps < .05$). $\Delta R^2 = .02$ for step 2. Information recall. $R^2 = .36$ for step 1 ($ps < .00$). $\Delta R^2 = .18$ for step 2 ($ps < .00$). $\Delta R^2 = .09$ for step 3 ($ps < .01$).

*** $p = .000$ ** $p < .005$. * $p < .05$.

4.4.4 *Value-based involvement, affect and win-win preponderance*

The final mediation hypothesis to be tested was concerned with the relationship between value-based involvement and win-win preponderance. Value-based involvement was neither a significant predictor for the valence latent growth curve nor for the average arousal. Thus, the mediation hypothesis had to be rejected.

5 DISCUSSION

On a summary and discussion of the results of this study (5.1) follows a presentation of its strengths and weaknesses (5.2). Finally, I derive some suggestions for the conflict resolution and mediation practice (5.3).

5.1 SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

How does identity association influence conflict resolution behavior? The computer scenario PeaceMaker was used in order to find some preliminary answers to that question in a controlled setting. Most importantly, results clearly demonstrated that far reaching consequences ensue when the identity of the conflict solver is associated with the conflict to be solved. In confirmation of the hypothesis H1, identity association was found to lead to a closed-minded conflict resolution strategy. Moreover, as anticipated in hypothesis H2, identity associated participants showed higher *arousal* levels and a stronger drop in affective *valence*. Valence and arousal mediated the relationship between identity and conflict resolution strategy.

5.1.1 Hypothesis 1: Identity association and closed-minded processing

Identity association leads to reliance on pre-existing cognitive structures

The reliance on pre-existing schemata and beliefs is part of a closed-minded thinking style. I supposed that an inclination to implement many win-lose actions in the conflict scenario can be plausibly interpreted as a sign of reliance on stereotypes about the role of the Israeli Prime Minister and on general conflict schemata as landmarks for decision-making. Conflict schemata are marked by a win-lose belief in the incompatibility of goals (Bar-Tal, Kruglanski, & Klar, 1999) and by “rigid thinking and black-white thinking” (Carnevale & Probst, 1998, p. 1300). Such a rigid, black-white thinking implicates an “either win or lose” attitude. Moreover, a stereotypical Israeli Prime Minister is primarily win-lose orientated. Results revealed that the more the conflict solvers’ *values* were associated with the conflict in Israel-Palestine, the more they tended towards a win-lose

stance in the game. This was true for those who had indicated affiliation with the Israeli side as well as for participants who felt affiliated with the Palestinian side – differences between these two groups were non-significant. Thus, the inclination to implement win-lose actions is not explainable by an *ex ante* given preference for the Israeli side. These findings particularly emphasize the important role of *values* for schema accessibility. Bar-Tal, Kruglanski and Klar (1989) theorized that conflict schemata should be highly accessible when they are related to values. The high predictive power of value-based involvement for the preponderance of a win-lose mental set corroborates this view.

Although the difference between Israel- and Palestine-affiliated participants in the implementation of win-lose actions did not reach significance, it followed the pattern observed by Gonzalez and Martin (2010). In their study, Palestine-affiliated participants implemented even more actions that favored the Israeli side than Israel-affiliated participants did. Also, in the present study Palestine-affiliated participants tended more towards win-lose than Israel-affiliated participants. This yields further evidence for the “naïve realism” approach (Robinson, Keltner, Ward, & Ross, 1995) which assumes that partisans overestimate the extremity of the other side’s stance. By implementing actions according to their “naïve” beliefs about the hawkishness of Israeli decision-makers, Palestine-affiliated participants accumulated higher win-lose scores.

Identity-associated participants not only relied on schemata and beliefs, but also on their conflict-specific knowledge. Knowledge was the best predictor for conflict resolution success. Due to their superior knowledge, high identity-associated persons were more successful in the conflict resolution than low identity-associated ones despite of adopting a win-lose stance. Apparently, the identity-associated participants were able to counterbalance the adverse effects of their win-lose stance by selecting the right, albeit fewer win-win actions. A reliance on pre-existing mental structures was thus at the same time favorable and unfavorable. This touches upon the ongoing debate as to under which conditions elaborate, effortful thinking and under which conditions thinking based on judgmental shortcuts and schemata leads to better decisions (e.g., Deutsch & Strack, 2008; Dijksterhuis, 2004). The current study provides evidence that schematic processing results in superior problem solving for persons with expertise in a given topic; i.e., with

knowledge about it (for further empirical evidence supporting this idea see Garcia-Retamero & Dhimi, 2009).

Identity association leads to less consideration of new information

Those who had indicated a *Jewish or Muslim* orientation accessed considerably fewer information sources than Christian or non-religious participants. In addition, gamers who felt generally *affiliated* to Israel or Palestine showed worse performance in a free recall task about the information provided in PeaceMaker when controlled for the frequency of information use. This finding is noteworthy as the Muslim and Jewish groups were - with the exception of one participant - sub-parts of the broader Palestine- or Israel- affiliated groups. Thus, identity association on the base of *affiliation* impaired the integration of novel information in existing cognitive structures or its subsequent retrieval, as expressed in worse recall. However, it did *not* influence information access behavior. Information use was only lower in case of an association of the conflict with the persons' *religion*. These differential effects found for the different facets of identity-conflict association may be worth further investigation. However, the single relationships which emerged here are clearly components of one big picture, a picture showing a strong link between identity association and closed-minded processing.

5.1.2 Hypothesis 2: Closed-minded processing and affect

A change in valence reduces the use of information sources

Whether participants felt comparatively more positive or negative affect at *one single measuring point* did not prove crucial for processing strategy. Instead, the *development of valence* in a latent growth curve predicted the subsequent frequency of information access. A drop in pleasure, measured over minute 0, minute 10 and minute 20, resulted in less information accessed between minutes 14 to 28. The valence rate of change did *not* predict the access of information sources in the first part of gaming (minutes 0-14). This provides support for a causally antecedent role of affect. The change of affective valence fully mediated the relationship between religion and information access in the second part of gaming. Muslim and Jewish participants felt better than

Christian and non-religious participants at the beginning, but already 10 minutes later, they felt worse. In the terminology of Lazarus (1991), they first felt challenged and then threatened. By contrast, the affective valence of the groups with a lowly conflict-associated religion showed greater stability. As a consequence of the switch from challenge to threat, highly identity-associated participants accessed very few information sources in the second gaming period. With tools like the latent growth curve modeling, changes of the affective experience can be assessed very reliably. The strong impact of affective change found in this study shows that it may be worth investigating further in that direction. In the vast majority of studies conducted until now (i.e., Bless et al., 1996; Isen, Niedenthal & Cantor, 1992), it was not even assessed how participants felt before the affect manipulation (baseline measures).

In a recent review, Blanchette and Richards (2010) called for more research on the impact of affect on working memory. The current findings suggest that the drop in pleasure may have depleted working memory resources (Ellis & Ashbrook, 1988). It is highly plausible that a pronounced change in affective valence caused ruminative thinking and other task-irrelevant cognitive activity which reduced the mental capacities available for the criterion task. In order to access the information sources, players need to shift their attention purposefully towards it. There is reasonable agreement in the field that affect has an impact on the shifting function of the central executive (Derakshan & Eysenck, 2010) and this is corroborated by the present results. Since Complex Problem Solving is highly capacity-demanding, working memory may be a particularly fruitful future research object in this field. So far, findings on the role of emotions in CPS are ambiguous (Barth & Funke, 2010; Sperring, Wagener, & Funke, 2005).

Results are inconsistent with Fiedler's (2001b) affect-cognition model or Bless' (2000) mood-and-general knowledge theory. Firstly, according to these models, the positive affect of highly identity associated participants at the beginning of the game should have predicted the schema-based strategy they pursued. However, this relationship was non-significant. Secondly, the decrease in valence experienced by the highly identity associated participants should have acted as a signal that attention needs to be directed to the details in the environment (accommodation in terms of Fiedler). Contrarily, persons looked at fewer information sources. However, these models are

based on experiments, where incidental affective states were induced, e.g., by music or movies. In the present study, the affective reaction was evoked by the task itself. The resulting affective experience may have been different and the models therefore not applicable.

It seems likely that the relevance and personal meaning of the setting where the affective state is experienced is decisive for the impact of affect on cognition. The crucial question might be: Do we have a context, in which persons actually *care* about their affective feelings? Once affect elicits rumination or worries, it detracts attention from details of the task and can therefore impede an information-based, open processing. In tasks of high self-relevance, as is the resolution of the Israeli-Palestinian conflict for identity-associated participants, persons may be highly susceptible to their affective states and the perception of affective changes may prompt self-focused attention. Studies on attentional focus have shown that a decrease in affect, which was induced by a self-relevant task, elicited self-focused as compared to external-focused attention (Sedikides, 1992). Thus, decreases in valence elicited by self-relevant tasks may not act as an adaptive signal triggering a focus on external details, but may instead prompt self-focused, distracting meta-cognitions. In previous studies demonstrating information-driven processing for task-related negative affect, the criterion task was not very self-relevant and affect did accordingly not cause a focus on the self (e.g., Spring, Wagener & Funke, 2005).

In general, most research on affect and cognition used contents that were not particularly meaningful for the participants and findings are of little significance for self-relevant real-world contexts and intense real-world emotions. By contrast, PeaceMaker is highly realistic and its semantic content was meaningful and personally involving for the participants.

High arousal reduces the recall of information sources

Those who reported affiliation with the Israeli or Palestinian side felt more aroused and listed less information sources in a delayed recall test. Scholars like Dörner (2002), Easterbrook (1959) and Kahneman (1973) predict a narrowing of attention for high arousal levels, expressed, for instance, by neglecting peripheral cues. Information

sources in PeaceMaker are peripheral and should therefore not be attended to in states of high arousal. In contrast to these expectations, low attendance to information sources was not predicted by high arousal levels. Arousal solely predicted the recall performance.

However, akin to valence, the current findings on arousal provide support for the capacity models discussed. Humphreys and Revelle (1984) suggested that high arousal impairs working memory functioning. Since working memory activity precedes the storage of information in long-term memory (see for example the Atkinson-Shiffrin memory model, Shiffrin & Atkinson, 1969) one can validly assume that high arousal may cause worse recall in threatening contexts, as observed in this study. Supporting this view, an obstructive impact of highly arousing contents on cued recall was found for television messages (Lang, Bolls, Potter, & Kawahara, 1999). The results are also consistent with models on threat effects, e.g., Dörner's "intellectual emergency reaction" (Dörner et al., 1994), which postulates an impaired storage of novel information given high arousal levels. Overall, the current findings are evidence that anxiety-like affective states in terms of displeasure and raised arousal can result in reduced attention to peripheral information and worse information encoding or retrieval.

Restrictively, it must be mentioned that arousal levels reported by the participants in this study were not very high. However, they may have underestimated or understated their arousal because its source was "only" a computer game. In fact, it should be noted that arousal as well as valence assumed a mediating role although they were in a medium range. In real-world conflicts, where affective reactions are clearly more intense, identity association is likely to show an even stronger impact on the conflict resolution mode. This urges mediation and conflict resolution practice to take identity into account in order to prepare appropriate countermeasures against the closed-mindedness of the actors involved.

5.1.3 Dual processing styles and conflict research

Those, who frequently accessed information sources, adopted a win-win stance and implemented fewer and less random actions. Thus, an open, information-driven conflict resolution style was followed. Subjects, who looked at little information, tended

towards a win-lose stand and implemented many actions in a random fashion. Thus, a schematic, closed-minded conflict resolution style was followed. Indicators of a closed and open strategy were interrelated as expected. The team around DeDreu successfully applied a dual process approach in negotiation research (DeDreu, Koole, & Oldersma, 1999; DeDreu, Koole, & Steinel, 2000). The present study provides additional evidence that it may be fruitful for conflict research to distinguish a systematic, information-based, effortful, from a closed-minded, knowledge-based, effortless strategy.

5.1.4 Identity association and feelings of control

Identity association was related to less fear of failing in the complex problem solving task and more feelings of dominance right before starting the game, also when controlled for the influence of knowledge. More specifically, Jewish and Muslim participants were significantly less afraid of failure, and stronger value-based involvement went along with more feelings of dominance in the first measure. This is explainable in terms of self-enhancement motivation. For identity-associated persons, the conflict resolution task was of greater personal importance. Thus, identity association may have increased perceived threats to the self-worth conveyed by the task. Conway and Howell (1989) and Robins and Beer (2001) have shown that involvement in a task leads to positive self-schema activation and a self-enhancement bias. Thus, participants may have activated positive self-related cognitions in order to reduce fear to fail and to augment feelings of control. Robins and Beer (2001) demonstrated further that self-enhancement is related to an increase in positive affect. In the present study, highly identity associated participants reported on higher levels of positive affect right before gaming as compared to the lowly identity-associated group. This affective reaction may be a result of positive self-related cognition in response to the self-threatening task. In fact, self-serving thoughts explain nicely why the identity associated group appraised the gaming context as more pleasant and thus challenging at the beginning.

5.2 STRENGTHS AND WEAKNESSES

The sample of this study was large and culturally diverse. However, generalizability may be diminished since it comprised only students and mostly participants interested in the topic (Brennan, 1983). Also, latent variable models are generally assumed to require a more extensive database. However, Hu and Bentler (1995) demonstrated that latent models calculated with small samples yield stable estimators and allow the detection of misfit. Signs of heteroscedasticity of residuals for the predicted variables *information use I* and *information use II* suggested some caution for generalization of the model to the population for these criterion variables.

This study stands out for explicitly considering the role of emotional arousal. Only recently it has been noticed that this important dimension is too often neglected despite of being intimately tied to processing capacity (Blanchette & Richards, 2010). The present findings underline the relevance of arousal particularly for memory-related processes. However, the assessment of the emotional experience in this study was very basic. Future research could use an appraisal tendency framework (e.g., Smith & Kirby, 2001) in order to examine how identity association influences the appraisal of a conflict and how the appraisal-contingent emotions impact the conflict resolution style. Distinct emotions are likely to have differential effects on reliance on general knowledge structures and peripheral information (Bodenhausen, Sheppard, & Kramer, 1995).

By making use of the very realistic PeaceMaker simulation, a high degree of external and internal validity was reached. However, PeaceMaker has its disadvantages. First, it is a commercial computer game and the ImpactGames company does not give the permission to change it. Typical Complex Problem Solving scenarios (e.g. MOROLAND, see Otto, Döring-Seipel, & Lantermann, 2002) allow the manipulation of its variables and scholars can examine the effects of scenario features. By contrast, the scope of hypotheses to be tested with PeaceMaker is limited. Moreover, the game's underlying formal structure was unknown and about the effects of the gamers' actions in the functional logic of the scenario could only be hypothesized.

However, this is more than made up for with the ecological validity of PeaceMaker, which is exceptionally high. Doubtlessly, the greatest strength of this study

consists in its importance for real-world problems. Inter-individual differences like religion and value-involvement influenced conflict resolution behaviour in the laboratory and will arguably have an even bigger impact in a real conflict situation. The relevance of identity cannot be underrated. Much research on the interactionist relationship between cognitive and affective factors was done with simple tasks that lacked meaning for the participants (see the review by Blanchette and Richards, 2010). The current study provides confirmatory evidence for the affect-cognition relation from a complex, ecologically valid and personally meaningful setting. This may encourage future research in cognitive and social psychology to make attempts to increase the studies' ecological validity.

Clearly, the significance of identity for conflict resolution needs to be examined in real-life conflict situations. The theory section of this paper makes some suggestions for variables to be considered. Particularly, the role of *cognitive commitment* (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984; Langer 1994) and *motivation for closure* (Kruglanski, 2004) in conflict is a research topic that may yield relevant insights in how to optimize conflict resolution and mediation practice. First and foremost, future research should address the question how despite a given identity involvement an information-based instead of a schema-based conflict resolution mode can be facilitated. This would be of great value for optimizing mediation techniques.

5.3 IMPLICATIONS FOR THE CONFLICT RESOLUTION PRACTICE

The present study shows on the basis of empirical findings why conflict resolution processes can be so extremely difficult. Often, the identity of opponents in a political or social conflict is strongly involved in the dispute, which brings with it the risk of closed-mindedness. Since identity association leads to stronger affective reactions, less consideration of novel information, less integration of new information in existing cognitive structures, as well as more reliance on conflict schemata and narrow pre-existing win-lose categories, it severely impairs advancements in conflict resolution. Identity-associated opponents maintain their stereotype-biased perceptions of each other and think in conflict structures instead of validly assessing the situation based on

the given facts. The present results highlight the importance of third party mediation in conflict resolution processes with high identity involvement. A mediator is urgently needed for the sake of external affect regulation and for helping opponents to change their perceptions and attitudes to each other and the conflict. Or to put it differently, a mediator has the important task to transform the conflict actors' processing mode into an information-based style and to dissolve the existing rigidities.

An open style corresponds to the *receiver perspective* in terms of Zajonc's (1960) classical model on the process of cognitive tuning in communication: "When a person primarily anticipates receiving information, he may be expected to activate a cognitive structure capable of admitting the incoming information. Concomitant with the anticipation of receiving information is the anticipation of cognitive change" (Zajonc, 1960, p. 161). A receiver is contrasted with a transmitter perspective. Whether cognitive structures for receiving or transmitting information are activated depends, according to Zajonc, on the role someone expects to assume in the communication. Therefore, a mediator needs to create a setting in which at least one of the conflict parties is put into a receiver position. In the mediation triad, transmitting and receiving roles can be interchanged. By establishing the genuine anticipation in one or both of the opponents to be bound to the listener role, new information is considered and more flexible cognitive structures are adopted which are susceptible to change.

However, in order to attend to and process the information provided conflict actors need to have enough cognitive resources and motivation. The motivation of the conflict actors to understand the intricate situation correctly can be enhanced by reframing the conflict as a complex problem to be solved. This elicits a more analytic processing mode and helps the opponents to dissociate from the question of who is right and who is wrong. Equally important is cognitive capacity. The current findings highlight that affect, in terms of valence and arousal, can decrease the resources available for receiving information. As soon as opponents of a conflict become highly aroused or develop a negative mood, self-focused attention and preoccupation with the own affective state may result. This depletes capacity for information processing. The present study shows that strong affective responses are particularly probable when the conflict parties' identities are associated with the conflict. In this case, a mediator needs to

monitor the affect of conflict actors with particular attention. The study results demonstrate that the intensity of affective *change* during conflict resolution, in contrast to the absolute affect levels, may be decisive for the cognitive capacity available. Persons who perceive a strong drop in affective valence usually attempt to regulate the negative mood. Unfortunately, affect regulation is often highly capacity-demanding (e.g., Gross, 1998; Otto & Lantermann, 2004). Thus, in order to counteract capacity cut-backs in the conflict actors, a successful mediator needs to address the affective dimension when dealing with highly identity-involved clients.

Different strategies of affect regulation are at a mediator's disposal (adapted from Gross, 1998). Highly relevant for mediation is a strategy commonly referred to as *situation selection*. Adapted to the context of mediation, situation selection means to create a setting in which emotional reactions are unlikely, for instance by carefully selecting the location and the environmental stimuli. A further useful regulation strategy is *attention distraction*. Here, a mediator brings into focus the non-emotional aspects of the problem or interrupts the emotional situation altogether. Apart from that, mediators can attempt to change the conflict parties' *cognitive appraisal* of the situation and by that they alter the situation's affective impact. For instance, to frame the situation ex ante as a collaborative problem solving setting instead of a stereotypical conflict resolution would be a form of cognitive change which results in less arousal and displeasure. Ideally, a positive affective state is evoked which is known to facilitate attentional breadth and cognitive flexibility (e.g., Fredrickson, 2001). Carnevale and Isen (1986) even found in a negotiation study that people in whom positive affect have been induced adopted a win-win stance and were less defensive. The current mediation practice could capitalize on this strength of affect through positive mood induction, e.g. via music or a pleasant meeting location.

Based on the work presented in this paper, particularly by Zajonc (1960), Bar-Tal, Kuglanski & Klar (1989) and Carnevale & Probst (1998), it becomes apparent that mediators need to devote special attention to the framing of the mediation situation since expectations determine the activation of cognitive structures. Identity-associated persons anticipating a tense setting activate conflict schemata that are win-lose-minded and rigid, whereas for successful conflict resolution, cognitive flexibility is advantageous.

In the present study, different forms of identity-conflict association have impacted affect and processing mode differently. Hence, conflict mediation may benefit from knowledge about the type of identity-conflict associations to deal with in a specific setting. Particularly values have proven to result in rigid, win-lose minded ways of thinking. In order to reduce this unfavorable impact of value-based involvement, it may help to call on opponents to reflect on the meaning of the conflict topic for their personal value system. However, further research is needed to disentangle the different facets of identity-conflict associations.

In the dawn of the 21th century, conflicts are ubiquitous. Empirical research in controlled settings contributes to a better understanding of the psychological factors which impair conflict resolution. On the long-term, I hope, this knowledge can help make the world a more peaceful place.

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APPENDIX

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APPENDIX A

A1. Schematic illustration of the two-dimensional structure of affect (adapted from Feldman Barrett and Russell, 1999).

A2. The effects of crises on cognitive performance and decision-making according to Holsti, 1990

APPENDIX B

B1. Classification of geo-cultural origin according to the United Nations

Western Europe	Eastern Europe	Western Asia		United States
- Austria	- Belarus	<i>Other areas</i>	<i>Conflict areas</i>	
- Belgium	- Bulgaria	- Armenia	- Israel	
- France	- Czech Republic	- Georgia	- Palestinian territories	
- Germany	- Hungary	- Iraq		
- Liechtenstein	- Poland	- Jordan		
- Luxembourg	- Republic of Moldova	- Lebanon		
- Monaco	- Romania	- Saudi Arabia		
- Netherlands	- Russian Federation	- Syrian		
- Switzerland	- Slovakia	- Turkey		
	- Ukraine	- United Arab Emirates		
		- ...		

Retrieved from <http://esa.un.org/unpp/definition.html>

B2. Assessment of English proficiency

	Self-rated grade	Time abroad (months)	Self-rated grade	Time abroad (months)
5 (excellent)	1-1,5	> 6		
4 (surpassing)	1-1,5	1-6	2	> 6
3 (very good)	1-1,5	0	2-2,5	>1
2 (good)	2-2,5	0	2-2,5	>1
1 (sufficient)	2-3,5	0	4	>1

Explanation. The self-reported grade was corrected for the the time spent abroad, e.g., a person with a 1,5 grade but who had spent only 2 months abroad was rated as surpassing instead of excellent.

B3. Academic fields of study participants

Academic field	N
Psychology	51
Political Science	10
Islamic sciences/ Jewish studies	18
Economy	3
Law	4
History	12
Behavioral and cultural sciences (other)	8
Natural sciences	18

B4. Categorization and scoring of win-lose and win-win actions

Win-Lose		Score	Win-Win		Score
Send army units:	Secure area	2	Remove army units		1
	Arrest Palestinian militants	3			
	Destroy infrastructure	4			
Send police units:	Police patrol	2	Remove police units		1
	Secure Area	2			
Add checkpoints		3	Remove checkpoints		3
Increase curfews		4	Ease curfews		4
Missile strike:	On militants' headquarters	4	Release prisoners		2
	On government infrastructure	4	Talk to Palestinian President:	Ask for anti-militant support	2
	On Palestinian police forces	4		Demand anti-militant action	1
Kill militant:	Apache strike	4	Listen to concerns		3
	Covert operation	3			
Bulldoze routes:	For clearing routes	3	Promise concessions		4
	As response to militant attacks	4	Promise reconstruction		4
Speech:	About Israel's security	3	Speech:	About peace	4
	Anti-militancy	1		Palestinian cooperation	4
Talk to government:	Promise more security	2	Government:	Ask to unite for peace	3
				Withdrawal support	3
Yesha issues	Promise concessions	2	Yesha:	Ask for restraint	2
				Suppress violence	2
				Arrest extremists	2
Talk to world leaders:	Ask for pressure on Palestine	3	World leaders	Mediation support	3
Increase trade restrictions		4	Decrease trade restrictions		4
Decrease worker permits		4	Increase worker permits		4
Expand existing settlements		3	Freeze settlement construction		3
Build new settlements		4	Remove existing settlements		4
Build more fence	On green line	3	Remove part of the fence		3
	On Palestine land	4			
			Allow refugee immigration		4
			Authorize refugee compensation		4
			Give reconstruction aid		4
			Fund Palestinian education		4
			Fund medical institutions		4
			Cultural initiatives		3

APPENDIX C

C1. Questionnaires on affiliation, value-based involvement, fear of failure and knowledge

Variable	Source	Likert-Scale	α	M	SD	Range
Affiliation	Own	(-3) "Israeli side" – (+3) "Palestinian side"	.97	3.97	1.53	1-7
Items						
1. In discussions about the Israeli-Palestinian conflict I rather support (...). 2. I feel more strongly associated with (...). 3. I sympathize more strongly with (...). 4. I rather identify with (...). 5. I have a stronger relationship with (...).						
Value-involvement	Cho & Boster, 2005	(1) "strongly disagree" – (5) "strongly agree"	.81	3.02	.72	1.2 – 4.2
Items						
1. The values that are the most important to me are what determine my stand on the conflict in the Israeli-Palestinian conflict. 2. Knowing my position on the Israeli-Palestinian conflict is central to understanding the kind of person I am. 3. My position on the Israeli-Palestinian conflict has little to do with my beliefs about how life should be lived (reversed coded). 4. My position on the Israeli-Palestinian conflict is based on the values with which I try to conduct my life. 5. The Israeli-Palestinian conflict is relevant to the core principles that guide my life. 6. My beliefs about how I should live my life determine my position on the Israeli-Palestinian conflict. 7. My position on the Israeli-Palestinian conflict reflects who I am.						
Fear of failure (subscale)	Rheinberg, Vollmeyer & Burns, 2001	(1) "strongly disagree" – (7) "strongly agree"	.84	3.34	1.22	1.0-6.4
Items						
1. I feel under pressure to do this task well. 2. I'm afraid I will make a fool out of myself. 3. It would be embarrassing to fail at this task. 4. I think I won't do well at the task. 5. When I think about the task, I feel somewhat concerned.						
Knowledge	Author	-	-	4.34	2.99	0-9
Items						
1. <i>How is the peace plan called that was presented by the Middle East Quartet in 2002?</i> a) 6-Point-Plan b) Annapolis-Accord c) Roadmap d) Peace Manual 2. <i>Which islamic sanctuary is on the temple mount in Jerusalem?</i> a) Al-aqsa mosque b) Al-haram mosque c) Quibla d) Prophets' mosque 3. <i>What is meant with the two Intifadas?</i> a) Two periods of strict boycotts of Palestinian products through Israel						

- b) Two Palestinian uprisings against Israeli rule where many were killed on both sides
 c) Two periods of non-violent Palestinian uprisings
 d) Two periods where the temple mount was temporarily occupied by Israeli troops
4. *Where is the Fatah predominant?*
 a) In West Jerusalem
 b) In the Gaza Strip
 c) In the West Bank
 d) In the South Lebanon
5. *Who proclaimed the autonomous state of Israel?*
 a) David Ben Munweis
 b) Benjamin Durlis
 c) David Ben Gurion
 d) Ben Dreiwas
6. *What is not true for Yassir Arafat?*
 a) He was president of the autonomous Palestinian areas
 b) He was awarded the Nobel Peace Price
 c) He took a stand for an end of the second Intifada?
 d) He co-founded the Fatah
7. *Which party did Ariel Scharon leave in 2005?*
 a) Schas
 b) Likud
 c) Avoda
 d) Kadima
8. *The peace plan from 1993, which was the first direct agreement between the government of Israel and the Palestine Liberation Organization (PLO), is called*
 b) Madrid Accords
 c) Helsinki Accords
 d) Prague Accords
 e) Oslo Accords
9. *What is not true for the Gaza Strip?*
 a) He is one of the territorial units forming the Palestinian territories
 b) He is situated on the Eastern coast of the Mediterranean Sea
 c) In 2005 there was a complete Israeli withdrawal
 d) Its largest town is Chan Yunis

Identification Own (1) "strongly disagree – $\alpha=.62$ M=4.23 SD=1.81 Range:1-7
 (2) "strongly agree"

Items:

1. I did not identify with role of the Israeli Prime Minister that I assumed in the game.
2. My identification with the position of the Prime Minister was high.

C2. The valence, arousal and dominance scales of the Self-assessment Manikin by Bradley and Lang (1994)

Valence scale

Arousal scale

Dominance scale

C3. Factor loadings of the items of the Questionnaire on Current Motivation (Rheinberg, Vollmeyer & Burns, 2001)

Item	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3	Factor 4
1. I like computer games. (I)	-.11	.64	-.21	.34
2. I think I am up to the difficulty of this task. (P)	-.15	.27	-.69	.00
3. I probably won't manage to do this task. (P-)	.15	-.07	.81	.10
4. While doing this task I will enjoy playing the role of politician who takes decisions in a political conflict. (I)	-.10	-.06	.10	.72
5. I feel under pressure to do this task well. (A)	.74	.02	-.10	.07
6. This task is a real challenge for me. (C)	.52	.34	-.13	.42
7. After having read the instruction, the task seems to be very interesting to me. (I)	-.05	.36	-.24	.63
8. I am eager to see how I will perform in the task. (C)	.08	-.34	-.67	.11
9. I'm afraid I will make a fool out of myself. (A)	.89	-.06	.11	.06
10. I'm really going to try as hard as I can on this task. (C)	.11	.30	.18	.53
11. For tasks like this I don't need a reward, they are lots of fun anyhow. (I)	-.06	.60	-.10	.55
12. It would be embarrassing to fail at this task. (A)	.74	-.11	.18	-.03
13. I think everyone could do well on this task. (P)	-.05	.72	.04	.18
14. I think I won't do well at the task. (P-)	.70	.07	.11	-.28
15. If I can do this task, I will feel proud of myself. (C)	.20	.74	.12	-.07
16. When I think about the task, I feel somewhat concerned. (A)	.69	-.05	.22	-.14
17. I would work on this task even in my free time. (I)	-.20	.53	-.07	.47
18. I feel petrified by the demands of this task. (A)	.44	.07	.67	-.01

Note. In the authors' original factor solution: (A) = Anxiety, (C) = Challenge, (I) = Interest, (P) = Probability of success.

APPENDIX D

D1. Inter-correlations of identity variables.

	Religion ¹	Origin ²	Value-based involvement	Affiliation Israel	Affiliation Palestine
Religion	1	.56**	.37**	.16	.09
Origin	.56**	1	.39**	-.15	.29**
Value-based involvement	.37**	.39**	1	-.04	.18*
Affiliation Israel	.16	-.15	-.04	1	-.61**
Affiliation Palestine	.09	.29**	.18	-.61**	1

¹ Religion was dummy coded: 1 = highly conflict relevant religion (Jewish and Muslim); 2 = lowly conflict relevant religion (other)

² Origin was dummy coded: 1 = region affected by the conflict (Western Asia); 2 = region not affected

D2. Correlation of relevant control variables with conflict resolution indicators

	English	Knowld	Info I	Info II	Action I	Action II	Winwin	CORE	Domin.	BIAS	Fear
English	1	,039	,028	,013	,292**	,197*	,052	,175	,124	-,166	,193*
Knowledge	,039	1	-,026	-,125	,254**	,301**	-,155	,198*	,258**	-,290**	-,021
Info I	,028	-,026	1	,361**	-,190*	-,197*	,140	,148	,014	-,078	-,183*
Info II	,013	-,125	,361**	1	-,085	-,096	,181*	,138	,083	-,095	-,150
Action I	,292**	,254**	-,190*	-,085	1	,709**	-,119	,136	,095	-,023	,129
Action II	,197*	,301**	-,197*	-,096	,709**	1	-,147	,196*	,116	-,144	,081
Win-win ¹	,052	-,155	,140	,181*	-,119	-,147	1	,215*	,022	-,286**	-,411**
CORE ²	,175	,198*	,148	,138	,136	,196*	,215*	1	,031	-,486**	-,129
Dominance	,124	,258**	,014	,083	,095	,116	,022	,031	1	-,063	-,185*
BIAS	-,166	-,290**	-,078	-,095	-,023	-,144	-,286**	-,486**	-,063	1	,272**
Variability	,193*	-,021	-,183*	-,150	,129	,081	-,411**	-,129	-,185*	,272**	1
Fear	-,148	-,300**	,022	,047	-,227*	-,135	-,002	,002	-,313**	,114	,086

**p<.01. *p<.05

¹ win-win = win-win preponderance, win-lose score subtracted from win-win score

² CORE = combinatory success score

APPENDIX E

Appendix E1. Group differences in control variables

	Knowledge	English	Fear	One-way ANOVA results ¹
<i>Non-affiliated</i>	3.3 (2.7)	3.4 (1.4)	3.8 (1.0)	<i>Knowledge</i> : F (2) = 3.1, p < .05, Israeli- & Palestinian- aff. > non-aff.; <i>Fear</i> : F (2) = 3.0, p < .05; Israeli- & Palestinian- aff. < non-aff.
<i>Israeli- affiliated</i>	5.0 (3.0)	3.2 (1.3)	3.2 (1.2)	
<i>Palestine-affiliated</i>	4.4 (3.0)	3.1 (1.3)	3.2 (1.3)	
<i>Christian</i>	3.7 (2.9)	3.2 (1.3)	3.7 (1.2)	<i>Knowledge</i> : F (1) = 3.5, p < .01, Jewish > all others; <i>Fear</i> : F (4) = 2.5, p < .05, Jewish & Muslim < Christian;
<i>Muslim</i>	4.5 (3.6)	2.7 (1.3)	2.7 (1.2)	
<i>Jewish</i>	6.6 (1.9)	3.2 (1.2)	2.9 (1.2)	
<i>No religion</i>	4.4 (2.8)	3.7 (1.2)	3.2 (1.1)	
<i>Western Europe</i>	4.0 (3.0)	3.3 (1.3)	3.5 (1.2)	<i>Knowledge</i> : F (4) = 2.4, p < .06., Israel-Palestine > Western Europe, Middle East; <i>Fear</i> : F (4) = 2.1, p < .09, Eastern Europe < Western Europe
<i>Eastern Europe</i>	4.9 (2.7)	2.8 (1.4)	2.5 (1.0)	
<i>Israel-Palestine</i>	7.3 (2.0)	2.8 (.89)	3.1 (1.1)	
<i>USA</i>	4.8 (2.9)	5.0 (.00)	3.0 (1.5)	
<i>Middle East without IP</i>	4.1 (3.2)	3.1 (1.5)	3.2 (1.3)	
Whole sample	4.3 (3.0)	3.2 (1.3)	3.3 (1.2)	
Value-involvement	$\beta = .53^{***}$	--	$\beta = -.20^*$	

*** p < .001; * p < .05

Note. Red font marks groups for which significant differences were revealed. Post-hoc Bonferroni tests were used.

E2. Conflict resolution differences between the religion groups

Religion		Christian	Muslim	Jewish	None	One-way ANOVA results
Interval I	Group	8.8 (11.8)	2.8 (4.1)	2.9 (3.5)	13.3 (11.3)	<i>Groups:</i> F (4) =3.6, p < .01; non-religious & Christian > Muslim & Jewish; <i>Polls:</i> F (4) = 2.1, p < .09; non-religious > Muslim;
	Poll	3.7 (6.2)	.67 (1.8)	2.5 (3.5)	5.5 (6.5)	
	Action	12.5 (5.7)	12.2 (5.7)	14.9 (5.6)	14.2 (6.5)	
Interval II	Group	5.5 (7.9)	2.0 (3.7)	2.6 (6.1)	7.0 (7.4)	<i>Groups:</i> non-religious > Muslim & Jewish, p< .05; <i>Polls:</i> F (4) = 2.02, p < .10; non-religious > Muslim & Jewish;
	Poll	2.3 (4.3)	.93 (1.7)	1.6 (4.1)	4.5 (5.8)	
	Action	18.1 (9.2)	17.5 (5.9)	20.8 (6.9)	18.6 (7.1)	
Opening	Group	4.5 (6.3)	1.6 (2.6)	2.8 (3.5)	8.1 (7.6)	<i>Groups:</i> F (4) = 3.5, p < .01., non-religious > Muslim & Jewish; <i>Polls:</i> F (4) = 2.6, p < .05, non-religious > Muslim & Jewish;
	Poll	2.3 (3.9)	.33 (1.0)	1.4 (2.1)	3.7 (4.0)	
	Action	5.3 (2.8)	4.7 (2.7)	6.8 (3.1)	6.0 (3.3)	
Closure	Group	2.3 (3.9)	.33 (1.0)	1.4 (2.1)	3.7 (4.0)	
	Poll	5.3 (2.8)	4.7 (2.7)	6.8 (3.1)	6.0 (3.3)	
	Action	10.8 (5.4)	10.2 (3.6)	12.5 (4.4)	10.3 (3.8)	
First 10	No ww	6.4 (1.4)	6.4 (1.7)	6.5 (1.3)	6.7 (1.3)	
	No wl	2.6 (1.3)	3.1 (1.8)	2.4 (1.2)	2.7 (1.2)	
	Sc ww	52.6 (11.8)	55.2 (16.0)	53.2 (12.2)	54.5 (12.1)	
	Sc wl	10.0 (6.6)	13.3 (10.3)	11.7 (7.0)	12.0 (7.8)	
Total game	No ww	61.7 (8.6)	62.2 (14.2)	63.3 (5.8)	64.6 (10.6)	
	No wl	26.9 (7.8)	28.2 (11.2)	25.7 (6.9)	24.2 (11.0)	
	Sc ww	49.8 (7.6)	52.6 (12.9)	52.6 (6.1)	52.3 (8.8)	
	Sc wl	11.6 (4.5)	13.7 (6.8)	13.4 (4.4)	11.2 (5.6)	
Variability	.89 (.08)	.85 (.11)	.88 (.14)	.88 (.08)	<i>Recall groups:</i> F (4) = 4.5, p < .002; non-religious & Christian > Muslim & Jewish	
Lost game	1.1 (1.2)	1.1 (1.2)	.88 (1.0)	1.5 (1.0)		
Time 1 st	1490 (672)	1352 (631)	1521 (723)	1250 (601)	<i>Recall polls:</i> F (4) = 3.2, p < .02, , non-religious & Christian > Muslim & Jewish	
Total Time	2109 (259)	1977 (147)	2076 (274)	2018 (249)		
Bias	16.2 (30.08)	13.6 (23.7)	8.6 (14.7)	20.8 (25.9)		
Combi sc.	.32 (.24)	.30 (.11)	.40 (.26)	.29 (.21)		
Recall grp	2.3 (2.2)	.80 (1.3)	1.2 (1.6)	3.2 (2.3)		
Recall poll	1.2 (1.7)	.27 (.59)	.81 (1.5)	2.0 (1.9)		

Explanation of abbreviations: group = number of groups accessed; poll = number of polls accessed; action = action frequency; no ww/wl = number of win-win/win-lose actions; sc ww/wl = win-win/win-lose score; variability = action variability score; lost games = number of lost games; time 1st = time of the first game; combi sc. = cumulative success score; recall grp = recall of groups information; recall poll = recall of polls information

E3. Conflict resolution differences between the affiliation groups

Affiliation		None	Israeli	Palestine	One-way ANOVA results
Interval I	Group	10.5 (11.8)	7.0 (9.3)	7.7 (11.3)	
	Poll	3.8 (5.9)	3.6 (5.8)	3.0 (5.7)	
	Action	13.1 (6.3)	13.2 (5.1)	13.2 (6.6)	
Interval II	Group	7.00 (9.2)	5.00 (7.7)	3.5 (4.8)	<i>Groups: Non-affil. > Pal-affil., p < .05</i> <i>Polls: F (2) = 4.3, p < .02, Non-affil. > Pal-affil. & Israel-affil</i>
	Poll	4.3 (6.0)	2.5 (4.6)	1.3 (2.6)	
	Action	18.8 (9.5)	18.0 (6.7)	18.8 (8.4)	
Opening	Group	5.00 (6.3)	4.5 (6.2)	4.5 (6.3)	
	Poll	2.4 (3.3)	2.2 (3.4)	2.0 (4.0)	
	Action	5.3 (3.2)	5.8 (2.6)	5.4 (3.1)	
Closure	Group	3.2 (5.6)	2.0 (4.8)	1.0 (3.1)	<i>Polls: Non-affil. > Pal-affil. & Israel-affil, p < .10</i>
	Poll	1.8 (3.3)	.67 (1.7)	.81 (1.3)	
	Action	10.3 (5.0)	11.2 (4.4)	10.8 (5.4)	
First 10	No ww ²	6.9 (1.2)	6.5 (1.3)	6.3 (1.5)	<i>Win-win: Pal-affil < non-affil, p < .05</i> <i>Win-lose: Pal-affil > non-affil, p < .08</i>
	No wl	2.3 (1.2)	2.6 (1.2)	2.9 (1.4)	
	Sc ww	58.0 (11.2)	53.0 (11.8)	51.4 (13.2)	
	Sc wl	9.7 (5.6)	11.4 (7.3)	11.3 (8.3)	
Total game	No ww	64.9 (9.0)	61.8 (7.9)	61.8 (11.0)	
	No wl	24.2 (8.8)	25.7 (7.4)	28.3 (9.7)	
	Sc ww	53.6 (7.6)	50.5 (7.3)	49.9 (9.6)	
	Sc wl	10.7 (5.0)	12.2 (4.6)	12.6 (5.4)	
	Variability	.88 (.08)	.89 (.10)	.88 (.10)	<i>Recall groups: F (2) = 5.8, p < .01, Non-affil. > Pal-affil. & Israel-affil</i> <i>Recall Recall polls: F (2) = 5.3, p < .01, Non-affil. > Pal-affil. & Israel-affil</i>
	Lost games	1.2 (1.1)	1.2 (1.3)	1.1 (1.0)	
	Time 1 st	1338 (660)	1400 (680)	1500 (645)	
	Total Time	2069 (231)	2074 (284)	2061 (229)	
	Bias	18.5 (29.2)	15.5 (25.5)	14.6 (26.8)	
	Combi Sc	.30 (.19)	.33 (.24)	.33 (.23)	
	Recall grp	3.3 (2.0)	1.7 (1.9)	2.0 (2.3)	
	Recall poll	2.0 (2.0)	.98 (1.6)	.80 (1.3)	

E4. Conflict resolution differences between the geo-cultural origin groups

Geo-cultural origin		Western Europe	Eastern Europe	USA	Israel-Palestine	Middle East	One-way ANOVA results
Interval I	Group	10.2 (11.9)	6.2 (7.7)	2.3 (1.3)	2.4 (4.5)	2.6 (3.1)	<i>Groups:</i> F (4) = 2.8, p < .03, and <i>Polls:</i> F (4) = 2.3, p < .07 - Western Europe > Israel-Palestine & Middle East <i>Action:</i> F (4) = 2.0, p < .10, IP & USA > Western Europe
	Poll	4.4 (6.5)	3.1 (3.6)	1.3 (2.8)	1.2 (2.7)	.43 (.85)	
	Action	12.4 (5.4)	13.6 (6.5)	19.0 (8.2)	16.5 (4.8)	13.4 (7.9)	
Interval II	Group	6.00 (7.8)	1.8 (4.3)	.25 (.50)	4.8 (8.3)	3.0 (5.1)	
	Poll	2.9 (4.6)	.92 (2.8)	.00 (.00)	3.0 (5.7)	2.1 (4.6)	
	Action	17.7 (7.8)	19.0 (7.7)	21.0 (6.2)	22.6 (5.8)	19.6 (10.9)	
Opening	Group	5.6 (6.7)	4.5 (6.3)	1.8 (1.7)	1.4 (2.4)	1.5 (2.4)	<i>Groups:</i> F (4) = 2.3, p < .07 and <i>Polls:</i> F (4) = 2.4, p < .06, Western Europe > Israel-Palestine & Middle East; <i>Action:</i> F (4) = 2.4, p < .06, IP & USA > Western Europe
	Poll	2.8 (4.0)	2.1 (3.0)	.00 (.00)	.50 (.93)	.29 (.83)	
	Action	5.2 (2.8)	5.6 (2.5)	9.0 (3.5)	7.3 (3.1)	5.3 (3.2)	
Closure	Group	2.4 (5.0)	1.6 (4.2)	.00 (.00)	.00 (.00)	.00 (.00)	<i>Actions:</i> IP > Western Europe, p < .08
	Poll	1.2 (2.4)	.13 (.36)	.00 (.00)	.67 (1.0)	.57 (1.1)	
	Action	10.5 (4.7)	10.2 (4.5)	10.0 (7.1)	14.2 (2.1)	11.7 (7.6)	
First 10	No ww*	6.6 (1.4)	6.2 (1.1)	5.8 (.50)	6.1 (1.9)	6.7 (1.3)	<i>Win-lose score:</i> F (4) = 2.5, p < .05., Eastern Europe > Western Europe
	No wl	2.5 (1.2)	2.8 (1.3)	3.0 (.00)	2.9 (2.2)	2.9 (1.5)	
	Sc ww	54.1 (12.0)	50.2 (12.0)	50.0 (6.5)	49.4 (14.7)	57.3 (14.7)	
	Sc wl	9.7 (6.5)	15.7 (7.9)	14.1 (4.3)	13.9 (13.0)	11.3 (6.6)	
Total game	No ww	63.5 (9.4)	61.5 (6.6)	60.5 (6.5)	54.4 (13.0)	63.0 (9.0)	<i>Win-lose score:</i> F (4) = 2.7, p < .05, Israel-Palestine & USA > Western Europe <i>Win-win score:</i> Israel-Palestine < Western Europe, p < .05
	No wl	25.5 (9.1)	24.8 (7.4)	31.3 (4.5)	30.5 (8.5)	29.1 (7.8)	
	Sc ww	51.3 (8.5)	51.4 (7.1)	51.2 (5.4)	44.5 (10.3)	50.7 (8.1)	
	Sc wl	11.1 (4.9)	13.0 (4.1)	16.2 (3.7)	15.2 (5.6)	13.4 (5.3)	
	Variability	.88 (.08)	.86 (.14)	.96 (.02)	.91 (.09)	.88 (.11)	<i>Recall groups:</i> Western Europe > Middle East, p < .07 <i>Recall polls:</i> F (4) = 7.2, p < .03, Western Europe > Eastern Europe & Middle East <i>Combinatory score:</i> Israel-Palestine > Eastern & Western Europe, p < .05 <i>Time game 1:</i> Israel-Palestine > Eastern Europe, p < .10
	Lost ga.	1.2 (1.1)	1.4 (1.2)	1.0 (1.2)	1.0 (1.4)	1.1 (1.0)	
	Time 1 st	1418 (650)	1238 (623)	1572 (967)	1745 (802)	1390 (598)	
	Tot Time	2076 (259)	2028 (212)	2180 (286)	2157 (304)	1970 (162)	
	Bias	16.1 (29)	23.8 (24.3)	2.3 (10.5)	12.4 (26.2)	13.2 (16.6)	
	Combi S.	.31 (.22)	.27 (.11)	.39 (.39)	.48 (.32)	.33 (.21)	
	Recall gr	2.5 (2.2)	1.7 (1.9)	1.3 (1.3)	1.5 (1.6)	1.4 (2.1)	
	Recall po	1.5 (1.7)	.54 (1.1)	.00 (.00)	.63 (1.4)	.43 (1.5)	

